

European Research Infrastructure supporting Smart Grid and Smart Energy Systems Research, Technology Development, Validation and Roll Out – Second Edition

Work Package WP10

JRA1 – Enhanced Validation Methods, Concepts, Procedures, and Benchmark Criteria

Deliverable D10.2

D-JRA1.2 Methods for Holistic Test Reproducibility

Funding Instrument: Research and Innovation Action
Call: H2020-INFRAIA-2019-1
Call Topic: INFRAIA-01-2018-2019 Integrating Activities for Advanced Communities

Project Start: 1 April 2020
Project Duration: 54 months

Beneficiary in Charge: OFFIS EV (OFFIS)

Document Identifier: doi:[10.5281/zenodo.8081442](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8081442)

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	✓
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the Consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the Consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Deliverable Information

Document Administrative Information	
Project Acronym:	ERIGrid 2.0
Project Number:	870620
Deliverable Number:	D10.2
Deliverable Full Title:	D-JRA1.2 Methods for Holistic Test Reproducibility
Deliverable Short Title:	Test Reproducibility
Document Identifier:	ERIGrid2-D102-TestReproducibility-submitted
Beneficiary in Charge:	OFFIS EV (OFFIS)
Report Version:	1.7
Contractual Date:	31/05/2023
Report Submission Date:	27/06/2023
Dissemination Level:	PU
Nature:	Report
Lead Author(s):	J.S. Schwarz, E. Schulte (OFFIS), K. Heussen (DTU)
Co-author(s):	J. Nikolettatos (CRES), L.E. Ramos Perez (DERlab), Z. Feng (UoS)
Keywords:	Uncertainty Quantification, Uncertainty Propagation, Co-Simulation, Laboratory, Design of Experiment, European Union (EU), H2020, Project, ERIGrid 2.0, GA 870620
Status:	<input type="checkbox"/> draft, <input type="checkbox"/> final, <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> submitted

Change Log

Date	Version	Author/Editor	Summary of Changes Made
07/12/2022	v1.0	J.S. Schwarz (OFFIS)	Draft structure for document
31/05/2023	v1.1	J.S. Schwarz, E. Schulte (OFFIS), K. Heussen (DTU), ..., Z. Feng (UoS)	Final draft ready for review
05/06/2023	v1.2	G. Silano (RSE)	Internal review
13/06/2023	v1.3	J.S. Schwarz, E. Schulte (OFFIS)	Incorporation of review comments
23/06/2023	v1.4	M. Calin (AIT)	Internal reiew
26/06/2023	v1.5	J.S. Schwarz (OFFIS)	Incorporation of review comments and final draft
26/06/2023	v1.6	E. Mrakotsky (AIT)	Language and grammar review
27/06/2023	v1.7	T. Strasser (AIT)	Final version

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	8
1. Introduction	10
1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document	10
1.2 Problem Statement / Motivation	10
1.3 Structure of the Document	11
2. Foundations	12
2.1 Uncertainty Analysis	12
2.2 Uncertainty Representation	17
2.3 Uncertainty Quantification	20
3. Process and Tools	25
3.1 Identification and Classification of Uncertainties	25
3.2 Toolbox for Sensitivity Analysis and Uncertainty Quantification	28
4. Guidelines	32
4.1 Educational Example Case	32
4.2 Typical Uncertainty Questions for Experiment Design	33
4.3 Experiment Setup Uncertainties	35
4.4 Guideline Overview	36
4.5 Methods and Approaches	37
5. Use Cases	56
5.1 Multi-Energy Benchmark	56
5.2 Multi-Energy District Flexibility	58
5.3 Example of Analytical Approach for Time Delay Compensation	59
6. Conclusions	66
References	67

List of Figures

Figure 1: Suggested attributes for uncertainty description (A) and their connection to the standard uncertainty classification (B) (Steinbrink, 2017).	14
Figure 2: Design of Experiment (DoE) as a part of the Holistic Test Description (HTD) workflow (Van Der Meer et al., 2018).	16
Figure 3: Taxonomy of types of representations of uncertainty (Steinbrink, 2017).	17
Figure 4: The Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) (above) and Probability Density Function (PDF) (below) of the standard normal distribution $\mathcal{N}(0, 1)$ (meaning a mean of 0 and a standard deviation of 1). One can see that the PDF is large where the CDF is steepest. ..	18
Figure 5: Schematic comparison of a mosaik scenario with a MoReSQUE scenario (Steinbrink, 2017).	24
Figure 6: System Breakdown (SBD) part of template for uncertainty in HTD.	26
Figure 7: System Configuration (SC) and Use Case (UC) part of template for uncertainty in HTD. ...	27
Figure 8: Purpose of Investigation (PoI) part of template for uncertainty in HTD.	27
Figure 9: Experiment Specification (ES) part of template for uncertainty in HTD.	28
Figure 10: Flowchart of the developed toolbox for sensitivity analysis and uncertainty quantification.	29
Figure 11: Comparison of different sampling methods.	44
Figure 12: Time series sampling approach.	47
Figure 13: Sobol indices for PV example.	48
Figure 14: Minimum and maximum values for Direct Normal Irradiance (DNI) and Power.	50
Figure 15: Uncertainty Propagation (UP) with Modular, Recognizing System for Quantification of Uncertainty with Ensembles (MoReSQUE) in a simulation of 36 hours.	51
Figure 16: Uncertainty Propagation (UP) with MoReSQUE in a simulation of 36 hours.	52
Figure 17: Validation and Uncertainty Quantification (Thacker et al., 2004, p.7).	53
Figure 18: Overview of the overall system configuration used in the multi-energy benchmark model.	56
Figure 19: Illustration of simulation results for multi-energy benchmark case study considering three variables: storage tank's inner diameter, Photo-Voltaic (PV) generation, self-consumption.	57
Figure 20: Schematic representation of the use case multi-energy district flexibility	58
Figure 21: Representation of simulation setups.	60
Figure 22: Representation of the equivalent model of the simulation setup.	61
Figure 23: Equivalent block diagram of the simulation setup in a SISO representation manner.	62
Figure 24: Simulation time delay between DPSL and PNDC over a selected period.	62
Figure 25: Histogram of simulation time delay distribution between DPSL and PNDC.	63
Figure 26: Histogram of simulation time delay normalised distribution between DPSL and PNDC and its relative probability.	63
Figure 27: Normalised probability density function of simulation time delay distribution between Dynamic Power System Laboratory (DPSL) and Power Network Demonstration Center (PNDC).	64

List of Tables

Table 1: Input parameters overview for the Toolbox for the definition of simulation parameterisation.	30
Table 2: Overview of the sampling and analysis methods in the toolbox.....	31
Table 3: Overview of approaches.....	38
Table 4: Uncertainty assessment, addressing question II.b.	38
Table 5: Analytical approach, addressing question I.a.	39
Table 6: Sampling approaches, addressing questions I.a, I.b, and II.a.	43
Table 7: Uncertainty propagation, addressing questions I.a, I.b, and III.b.	48
Table 8: System validation, addressing questions III.a, III.b.	53

List of Abbreviations

ANOVA	Analysis of Variances
ANN	Artificial Neural Network
CDF	Cumulative Distribution Function
CHP	Combined Heat and Power
CPES	Cyber-Physical Energy System
CT	Characterisation Test
DoE	Design of Experiment
DNI	Direct Normal Irradiance
DRTS	Digital Real-Time Simulation
DSO	Distribution System Operator
DSS	Dempster-Shafer Structure
DPSL	Dynamic Power System Laboratory
eFAST	extended Fourier Amplitude Sensitivity Test
ES	Experiment Specification
ESS	Energy Storage System
ExD	Experiment Design
ExS	Experiment Setup
GDRTS	Geographically Distributed Real-Time Simulation
HIL	Hardware-in-the-Loop
HTD	Holistic Test Description
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
ITM	Ideal Transformer Model
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LHS	Latin Hypercube Sampling
MC	Monte Carlo
MoReSQUE	Modular, Recognizing System for Quantification of Uncertainty with Ensembles
OA	Open Access
OAM	Output Aggregation Module
OAT	One (factor)-at-a-Time
OS	Open Source
PCC	Point of Common Coupling
PCE	Polynomial Chaos Expansion
PDF	Probability Density Function
PHIL	Power Hardware-in-the-Loop
PNDC	Power Network Demonstration Center
PV	Photo-Voltaic
PoI	Purpose of Investigation
RFV	Random Fuzzy Variables
QA	Quality Attribute
RI	Research Infrastructure
ROM	Reduced-Order Model
RSS	Root of Summed Squares
SA	Sensitivity Analysis
SALib	Sensitivity Analysis Library in Python
SBD	System Breakdown
SISO	Single-Input-Single-Output
Sol	System of Interest

SuT	System under Test
SC	System Configuration
UC	Use Case
UQ	Uncertainty Quantification
UQM	Uncertainty Quantification Modules
UP	Uncertainty Propagation
TC	Test Case
TCR	Test Criteria
TO	Test Objective
TM	Target Metric
TS	Test Specification
TSy	Test System
UA	Uncertainty Assessment
VA	Variability Attribute
VaT	Validation Test
VeT	Verification Test

Executive Summary

This document presents uncertainty representation and validation methods. The ERIGRID 2.0 project aims to enhance the research infrastructures' capabilities and supports the research and technology development towards smart energy systems in Europe. This work aims to present a set of statistical methods for the representation of uncertainty, propagation of uncertainty, and system validation and provide practical guideline material to show how these methods can be applied. In this context, some new tools were implemented, but the focus was more on making the methods practical available for potential users than on new research on the methods.

The motivation for this work stems from researchers in the domain of energy systems often employing laboratory experiments and computer simulations to evaluate their hypotheses. This process is riddled with different kinds of uncertainties, which often render results difficult to reproduce. The classical approach in the power systems domain has been to focus on deterministic experimental setups, but this approach limits the range of possible testing strategies. Since the potential impact of laboratory testing can be extended with the proper handling of uncertainties, a systematic approach to the analysis and accounting of uncertainty factors is required.

To support experimenters in considering, quantifying and potentially reducing uncertainty, we prepared a set of guiding questions. The following questions aim to categorise the experimental uncertainty issue at hand, in order to match the research challenge and identify a suitable approach. In each case, we give some guidelines and further references to help answering the question:

- I. (a) *How can the uncertainty of the 'main outcomes' be quantified?* This is the basic question, and in its answer, uncertainty will usually be specified in the form $y \pm \sigma_y$, where y is the experiment's outcome and σ_y is the expected deviation from this outcome.
- (b) *How can the uncertainty be systematically characterised?* To make the answer to the first question more precisely, uncertainty may be given as a (probability) distribution instead of just a single number. At the very least, this gives a specific meaning to the deviation σ_y in the previous question (for example, as the standard deviation of a normal distribution), but distributions that cannot be reduced to a single number are also possible.
- II. (a) *Which uncertain input parameter is dominant and introduces the most uncertainty on the outputs?* Having quantified the uncertainty, the next aim is often to reduce it. To concentrate one's efforts, it is advisable to determine where the uncertainty is coming from. Often, the inputs to an experiment or simulation will already be certain. By performing a sensitivity analysis, one can find out which of these inputs has the biggest effect on the output, or rather, which input's uncertainty is most relevant to the output's uncertainty.
- (b) *How can the uncertainty be further reduced (if possible)?* When aiming to reduce the uncertainty, one needs to distinguish between aleatory uncertainty (which is due to truly random fluctuation in the setup, input values or measurement devices) and epistemic uncertainty (which is due to lack of knowledge). Only the latter can effectively be reduced, as truly random processes do not lose their randomness under closer study (if they do, they were partially epistemic to begin with).

- III. (a) *How can the representational uncertainty of a computational test setup with respect to physical ground truth (real-world or laboratory) be characterised?* One particularly tricky form of uncertainty is representational uncertainty which comes from the fact that no model and no lab experiment can ever capture reality perfectly. This question is about figuring out how much the chosen model differs from the real world, and the uncertainties in the outputs resulting from this deviation.
- (b) *How can I estimate the accuracy of my experimental results by propagating representational uncertainty of a computational model?* Having determined values for the parameters of a computational model, potentially with some uncertainty, one can then run the model on further inputs to extrapolate the effect of extrinsic uncertainty. Facing the problem of quantifying the uncertainty in the computed outputs is stemming from the uncertainty in the parameter values.

To help answering these questions, several approaches are introduced:

- Guidelines on how to assess uncertainty, as an extension of the Holistic Test Description (HTD) template. For this, an additional Microsoft Office Excel template was developed, which supports the user in the process.
- An analytical approach for uncertainty propagation which requires an accurate mathematical description of the underlying model but no model evaluations.
- Several sampling approaches, including purely random Monte Carlo (MC) sampling and quasi-random Sobol sequences. These can be applied to any system, though they can be costly due to the high number of model evaluations that might be necessary. For using these different approaches, a toolbox was developed, which allows instantiating multiple simulation runs based on a JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) configuration file. Depending on the configuration, sampling approaches and analysis of data are automatically applied.
- The method of Sobol indices for sensitivity analysis.
- The tool MoReSQUE for uncertainty propagation of stateless simulators integrated into a co-simulation setup.
- System validation guidelines for investigating the representational uncertainty between a simulation model and an experimental setup.

For all approaches, examples are shown for a small educational example with uncertain irradiance and a PV system. Some more complex examples are used to highlight the advanced capabilities of the approaches in more detail. Additionally, the multi-energy benchmark is used as an example. The guideline example material and some of the use cases are available in an Open Access (OA)/Open Source (OS) repository.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

The goal of this work is to provide the statistical framework needed for test reproducibility and representation of data and result uncertainty. In the work description this goal is subdivided in (1) representation of uncertainty, (2) propagation of uncertainty, and (3) system validation.

In previous work of the ERIGrid project a concept for bringing together HTD and DoE was proposed which is extended in this research work. Benchmark scenarios are used as examples for the proposed approaches in this research activity. With these examples, the statistical framework is explained to make it better understandable and to provide examples for applications in holistic energy systems tests.

There exists a large set of literature about the handling of uncertainty and system validation. For different domains, different approaches are used and it is not always easy to identify a suitable approach for a given problem.

The goal of the document at hand is to provide guidelines for handling uncertainties in software and hardware experiments of the power system. Thus, a short introduction to the foundations of uncertainty handling is provided, but the focus is more on practical usage and examples. For more background information of specific methods and theories, references to more detailed information are provided. The examples aim to illustrate the usage of uncertainty handling approaches and will be based on results from ERIGrid and ERIGrid 2.0, if available.

As the goal is to achieve reproducibility and this term is sometimes confused with repeatability, these terms should be differentiated here. As stated in (Feitelson, 2015), *repeatability* describes the “*exact repetition of an experiment, using the same experimental apparatus, and under the same conditions*”, which might be used to calculate confidence intervals in setups where variations or measurement errors occur. On the contrary, *reproducibility* is defined as “*implementing the same general idea, in a similar setting, with newly created appropriate experimental apparatus*”. Thus, it is crucial for reproducibility to document the setup and all boundary conditions which might have an effect on the results.

1.2 Problem Statement / Motivation

Researchers performing energy systems experiments are facing various complications with uncertainty that often do not match straightforward with existing statistics textbook examples.

To aid researchers in their experimental design concerning uncertainty quantification, we propose a set of stereotypical research questions. Each question is associated with a different understanding of uncertainty in an experiment and leads to different methods.

To use this guideline, the experiment planner needs to identify which of the questions most closely matches their research question and their need for quantifying uncertainty aspects.

Here, we will give a short overview of these questions. They will come up again in Section 4.2 where we will link them to the guidelines and use cases in Sections 4 and 5.

- I. *What is the effective uncertainty of the experimental outcome?*
 - (a) *How can the uncertainty of the ‘main outcomes’ be quantified?* The easiest way of expressing uncertainty is by giving the best approximation of the target value y and a deviation σ_y , which expresses how much the actual value might differ from y . Often, the two values are specified together in the format $y \pm \sigma_y$. The precise interpretation of the deviation needs to be specified; common interpretations include the standard deviation (considering the computed value as a random variable) or as bounds of an interval.
 - (b) *How can the uncertainty be systematically characterised?* For additional explicitness, one can also specify probability distributions for uncertain values directly. This also enables greater flexibility over a singular uncertainty measure.
- II. *How can the uncertainty of the experimental outcome be reduced?*
 - (a) *Which uncertain input parameter is dominant and introduces the most uncertainty on the outputs?* To reduce uncertainty caused by uncertain inputs, it is useful to know which of the uncertain inputs are dominant. Then it is possible to focus the efforts on reducing the uncertainty of these input parameters.
 - (b) *How can the uncertainty be further reduced (if possible)?* In addition to improving the input uncertainty, one can also reduce uncertainty by gaining additional insight into the problem, thus reducing one’s epistemic uncertainty. On the other hand, truly aleatory uncertainty usually cannot be reduced.
- III. *How can the representational uncertainty of a simulation-based test setup be characterised and accounted for?*
 - (a) *How can the representational uncertainty of a computational test setup with respect to physical ground truth (real-world or laboratory) be characterised?* For cost reduction and performance improvement, hardware experiments are often implemented as simulations. To know how accurate the results of this simulation are, the results have to be compared with the hardware experiment.
 - (b) *How can I estimate the accuracy of my experimental results by propagating representational uncertainty of a computational model?* Having determined values for the parameters of a computational model, potentially with some uncertainty, one can then run the model on further inputs to extrapolate the effect of extrinsic uncertainty. One is then faced with the problem of quantifying the uncertainty in the computed outputs, stemming from the uncertainty in the parameter values.

1.3 Structure of the Document

This document is organised as follows: Section 2 provides the theoretical foundations of uncertainty quantification as the base for the later sections, Section 3 describes the process and tools developed in this work, and Section 4 contains the guidelines. Section 5 shows use cases applying the methods explained in the guidelines. The document is concluded in Section 6.

2 Foundations

Uncertainty Quantification (UQ) is the science of quantitative characterisation and reduction of uncertainties in both computational and real-world applications. It tries to determine how likely certain outcomes are if some aspects of the system are not exactly known.

UQ involves many different tasks, such as uncertainty propagation, sensitivity analysis, stochastic inference, model calibration, design of experiments, meta-modelling (surrogate models), and others (Zhang, Yin, & Wang, 2020). It is based on foundational ideas and techniques from statistics and applied mathematics, requiring a basic understanding from the analyst performing the uncertainty analysis in these fields. An overview of the relevant topics from statistics and applied mathematics is provided in this section. The foundations are directly explained and references to more detailed information in the related literature are given.

Additional to the knowledge about the methodology, also expertise in the field of the application under study is important. In the field of smart grids, there is a shift towards Cyber-Physical Energy System (CPES). Such systems include the interaction of various domains, like electrical, Information and Communication Technology (ICT), automation, markets, infrastructure, thermal, and more. A holistic test procedure, as proposed in the ERIGrid project, for the development, testing, and validation of new concepts, systems, and components consists of a complex process (Heussen et al., 2019). Due to its complexity, most often it will consist of a software simulation of a model of the process or a combination of parts of software simulation with physical experiments. Considering uncertainty in this complex environment is crucial for sound results.

In the following, the basics of uncertainty analysis are described in Section 2.1, different types of uncertainty representation are introduced in Section 2.2 and common methods for UQ are explained in Section 2.3.

2.1 Uncertainty Analysis

Uncertainty analysis investigates the effects of lack of knowledge or potential errors on model inputs (e.g., the uncertainty associated with parameter values) (Gaber, Foley, Pascual, Stiber, & Sunderland, 2009). In this section, first, the different uncertainty types are introduced and second processes for the identification and treatment of uncertainty are shown.

2.1.1 Uncertainty Types

In the context of modelling, there can be many sources of uncertainty. However, it is convenient to categorise the character of uncertainties as either aleatory or epistemic (Kiureghian & Ditlevsen, 2009). Clarification of the type of uncertainty is important for its correct handling.

Aleatory Uncertainty

This is uncertainty resulting from intrinsic fluctuations of a system like the irradiation of the sun. Thus, it is irreducible. A characteristic of a physical, hardware-based experiment is that a measured quantity contains a random error. Because of the random error even with the same values of the inputs, the response is non-repeatable. This necessitates the statistical analysis of the results through repetitions. It is related to the variability of repeatable events,

which arises from intrinsic randomness. It is sometimes also named stochastic, objective, or ontological uncertainty, randomness, or variability.

Epistemic Uncertainty

This type of uncertainty results from a lack of knowledge. It is therefore reducible by gaining more knowledge. A software-based experiment is usually 'deterministic', in the sense that if an experiment is repeated with the same input combination x the same response y will be observed. A deterministic computer program has no random variability as there is no random error in a computer experiment. However, even in a single event, there is uncertainty, not related to intrinsic randomness. For example, the parameters for the model of a power line, e.g., its impedance, maybe not exactly known. In this case, statistical analysis of results can be implemented in a sampling-based approach, by systematically repeating the experiment with varied input parameters according to a sampling design. Other terms for epistemic uncertainty are subjective or systematic uncertainty, or incertitude.

Uncertainty Flavours

Epistemic uncertainties may introduce dependence among random events, which may not be properly noted if modelled as aleatory variables (Mulenga, Bollen, & Etherden, 2021). Different data sets are needed for each type of uncertainty. For example, to obtain realistic results from practical hosting capacity studies, a survey may be conducted to determine the number of customers willing to install PV in the future. This will reduce the epistemic uncertainty about customer willingness, however, the actual number of PVs that will be installed is still unknown. This remaining uncertainty might then be modelled as aleatory, and the true value can only be determined by measuring (i.e., actually counting the installed PVs in the future).

According to (Steinbrink, 2017), uncertainty may be perceived from three different angles, as shown in Figure 1. *Uncertainty flavour* refers to the way in which analysts lack knowledge about aspects of reality, e.g., ignore information or phenomena because they are negligible. *Uncertainty manifestation* describes the characteristic of a simulation model about which uncertainty exists, like input data, model equations, model implementation, etc. *Uncertainty representation* indicates which uncertainty models may be used to mathematically describe the uncertainty about a given manifestation or source.

Model or Representational Uncertainty

Besides the differentiation between aleatory and epistemic uncertainty in the literature many definitions for different types of uncertainty exist, as can be seen in the overview of uncertainty type classification in different domains by Thunnissen (Thunnissen, 2003). Thus, the definition of a term in the concrete context is crucial. As mentioned in the questions (see Section 1.2), one important aspect is representational uncertainty. We lean our definition on the definition by (Gralla & Szajnfarter, 2016). In the domain of System Design and Operations, they define it as "An epistemic uncertainty in whether the system model represents reality well enough to do the next design steps." (Gralla & Szajnfarter, 2016, p.4)

This definition is similar to definitions of model uncertainty given by Thunnissen: "Model uncertainty is the accuracy of a mathematical model to describe an actual physical system of interest. [...] All models are unavoidably simplifications of reality which leads to a disturbing conclusion: every model is definitely false. However, some models are better than oth-

Figure 1: Suggested attributes for uncertainty description (A) and their connection to the standard uncertainty classification (B) (Steinbrink, 2017).

ers. [...] Model uncertainty arises from approximation, numerical, and programming errors.” (Thunnissen, 2003)

2.1.2 Uncertainty Identification and Treatment with HTD and DoE

Experimental design and analysis have to deal with a wide range of uncertainty sources and uncertainty types. Two established methodologies are available to structure the description of experimental plans (HTD) and to mathematically and algorithmically structure the analysis (DoE).

HTD and Uncertainty Considerations in Test Purposes

The HTD is an established approach to support the reproducibility of experiments (Heussen et al., 2019). It aims to support testing and test description by assisting practitioners in laying out the intentions for a complex CPES testing and defining the essential parameters and procedural steps for conducting a test. The HTD has been shown to be compatible with DoE concepts and methodology (Van Der Meer et al., 2018).

The HTD comprises three levels of test definition, where each references the previous level, leading to an incremental scoping of a concrete test or experiment. The sequence of specifications includes the following, each supported by relevant template forms and guiding text:

1. *Test Case (TC)* — in analogy to ‘use case’: defining the objectives and domains for a test.
2. *Test Specification (TS)* — defining test system and its parameters (What test is to be carried out?).
3. *Experiment Specification (ES)* — defining how the test specification is to be implemented in a given Research Infrastructure (RI).

The TC is an essential part of an experiment. In the test case template, three main parts can be identified. First, the Test Objectives (TOs) in narrative form, and their more analytical form as Pol; second, the description of system functions and components to organise the System under Test (SuT); and, finally, the Test Criteria (TCR), which present a further formalisation of the test objectives in terms of measurands of performance and behaviour.

The Pol differentiates between:

- *Characterisation Test (CT)*: A measure is given without specific requirements for passing the test.
- *Validation Test (VaT)*: Functional requirements and abstract measures are provided, but are subject to interpretation; qualitative test criteria.
- *Verification Test (VeT)*: Tests where requirements are formulated as quantitative measures and thresholds of acceptable values are quantified.

Following the textual formulation of Pols, the next step is the detailing of the TCR. The Target Metrics (TMs), variability attributes and quality attributes each identify parameters related to the SuT, to suitably measure, perturb and assess experiment result quality, respectively:

- *Target Metrics (TMs) (criteria)*: List of metrics to quantify each Pol.
- *Variability Attributes (VAs)*: Controllable or uncontrollable parameters to “disturb” SuT.
- *Quality Attributes (QAs) (thresholds)*: Test result level or quality of the TM required to pass or conclude the testing.

The *Test Specification* aims to clarify the relationship between the object under investigation, the test objective, and the configuration, means and method under which a test is to be carried out and evaluated (i.e., test system and test design). Related to the test specification is a system configuration that defines the details of the system under test, including the object under investigation, as well as the simplified interfaced elements at the SuT boundaries, offering a concrete quantitative formulation of the test objective.

In the *Experiment Specification*, the TS is mapped to the available components and functionality of the lab where the experiment is executed. This consists of two main parts: (i) the Experiment Setup (ExS), which reflects the Test System (TSy), and (ii) the Experiment Design (ExD). The latter must plan in detail and document all the needed information for the execution, evaluation, and replication of the test.

Design of Experiment (DoE)

To investigate the effects of variability and uncertainty in the inputs of an experiment, the parameter space has to be explored. For simulation of complex CPES, this parameter space is usually high-dimensional and contains an infinite number of possible combinations. From the perspective of technical testing, an objective in test planning and design can be formulated in the question: “Given my limited budget, how can I gain as much information as possible?” To this end, the DoE theory offers sampling strategies that maximise the information (Kleijnen, 2015; Giunta, Wojtkiewicz, & Eldred, 2003) which can be gained from a limited number of experiments.

The applicability of DoE to power systems and CPES testing has been demonstrated during the ERIGrid project, and a mapping to the ERIGrid HTD method has been provided (Van Der Meer et al., 2018). Whereas the HTD aids in scoping of an experiment (“What is the main purpose

of running this experiment?” and “What do I hope to be able to show?”), DoE provides a formal mathematical framework once the testing objectives, metrics and factor constraints have been clarified. As shown in Figure 2, by using the HTD process the DoE aspects should be already considered to implement a meaningful experiment. Especially, in the TS phase the factors for DoE should be already defined, so that the experimental design can be chosen in the ES.

Figure 2: DoE as a part of the HTD workflow (Van Der Meer et al., 2018).

In practice, it has been shown for more complex scenarios that a gap remains between the formulation of the HTD and the possibility of an algorithmic experimental design according to DoE. Thus, one aspect of this work is to describe extensions and additional guideline texts for the HTD. The HTD contained already some fields aiming to define uncertainty aspects, which were extended with additional explanatory texts and examples. Also, some missing aspects were found and new fields were added to the HTD template. A more detailed description of the changes can be found in Section 3.1.

For the implementation of DoE, some libraries exist to support users. Probably the most common library to refer to is the Sensitivity Analysis Library in Python (SALib)¹ (Herman & Usher, 2017; Iwanaga, Usher, & Herman, 2022), which contains many sampling and analysis methods. Some of these will be described in more detail and their usage will be shown later in this document. Some practical examples for DoE in the context of CPES were implemented in ERIGrid and published as part of a summer school (*ERIGrid/NA4-SummerSchool-DTU-2018: v2.0, n.d.*). It contains a simulation scenario based on the co-simulation framework mosaik² simulating a household with PV system and battery and an electricity grid simulation. Based on this simulation scenario, some DoE methods are shown and explained. One analysis methodology is the Analysis of Variances (ANOVA) which, among other applications, allows to analyse

¹<https://salib.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>

²<https://mosaik.offis.de>

the variation of the dependent variable subdividing into significant components, which are then systematically observed and treated (Walpole, Myers, Myers, & Ye, 2012). Therefore, ANOVA can be implemented for measuring the effect of a “treatment” or “procedure” applied in the dependent variable by comparing the variances of the groups. This is used in DoE to evaluate the effects of variations in variables that may be co-related. A second analysis method is meta-modelling, which builds a meta-model based on the simulation results to represent the impact of variations on the results. This implementation was used as the base for a toolbox for Sensitivity Analysis (SA) and UQ, developed in this research work and described in Sections 3.2 and 5.1.

2.2 Uncertainty Representation

A major task in UQ is to quantify the uncertainty in the outputs of a model or a system induced by uncertainty in inputs as outlined in Figure 3. To do this, we consider the process under study as a mapping of a vector $\mathbf{x} = \langle x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N \rangle$ of N input parameters (also called “factors”) to an output quantity y of interest:

$$y = f(\mathbf{x}).$$

More generally, the output can also be a vector $\mathbf{y} = \langle y_1, y_2, \dots, y_M \rangle$. However, it is usually possible to perform the analysis for each entry of that vector separately, so we will restrict it to the case of one output.

Figure 3: Taxonomy of types of representations of uncertainty (Steinbrink, 2017).

2.2.1 Capturing Aleatory Uncertainty

The mathematical representation of aleatory uncertainty in this context is well-established: it is the language probability theory. This is the most common way of quantifying uncertainty and statistical techniques are utilised for most tasks involved in UQ. As a very quick primer and to fix notation for the rest of the document, a short introduction is given here, for more information one could refer to any book on probability theory and/or statistics, for example, (Bain & Engelhardt, 1992).

In the probabilistic setting, the input vector \mathbf{x} is considered a vector of random variables, which means that the variable’s value is not known in a given case, but the potential values and their probabilities are. The notation followed in statistics is that a random variable is expressed by

an uppercase letter, while its particular value is denoted by a lowercase letter: for example, a random variable X_i and its value x_i . The output is now a random variable also, and the following formula shows the relation of the random variables through the model f :

$$Y = f(\mathbf{X}).$$

The information about a random variable is captured by its probability distribution. In the general case, these distributions are probability measures; however, in the case of single real-valued random variables and discrete random variables, more visual representations are available, see Figure 4.

Figure 4: The CDF (above) and PDF (below) of the standard normal distribution $\mathcal{N}(0, 1)$ (meaning a mean of 0 and a standard deviation of 1). One can see that the PDF is large where the CDF is steepest.

A real-valued random variable X can be expressed using a CDF F_X . Its value at a point $x \in \mathbb{R}$ is the probability that the value of X is at most x , i.e.

$$F_X(x) = \mathbb{P}(X \leq x).$$

(Here, $\mathbb{P}(E)$ stands for “the probability of E ”.) For two given realisations x_1, x_2 of X with $x_1 < x_2$, whenever $X \leq x_1$, the condition $X \leq x_2$ is automatically true as well. Therefore, the latter is at least as probable as the former, which implies that the function F_X is non-decreasing.

If one graphs this function, the areas where this graph is steep (or even jumps) indicate the most likely values for X . This motivates considering the derivative f_X of F_X (if it exists). This is called the PDF of X . Given the PDF, the probability that X falls in the interval $[a, b]$ can be expressed using an integral (this is essentially the Fundamental Theorem of Calculus):

$$\mathbb{P}(a \leq X \leq b) = \int_a^b f_X(x) dx.$$

Now, functions are nice to visualise but they still pose a problem in practice: a function consists of an infinite amount of information. One way around this is to restrict our attention to kernel

density estimators (Rosenblatt, 1956; Parzen, 1962). Given a sequence of values x_1, \dots, x_n (often obtained from some sampling process), consider the PDF:

$$f_X(x) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{\sigma} \varphi\left(\frac{x - x_i}{\sigma}\right),$$

where $\varphi(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-x^2/2}$ is the PDF of the normal distribution, and σ is the assumed standard deviation. Choosing the right value for σ will increase the rate at which the kernel density estimator converges to the 'true' distribution (Jones, Marron, & Sheather, 1996).

2.2.2 Capturing Epistemic and Combined Uncertainty

Methods for capturing epistemic uncertainty are considerably less-established. If sufficient statistical information is available, probability distributions may be used for this purpose as well. However, when there is incomplete knowledge, other non-probabilistic representations are more appropriate. Misrepresenting epistemic uncertainty through the wrong probability distribution – as a result of incomplete knowledge – can lead to faulty quantification of the output uncertainty. When the available data is scarce or only the upper and lower bounds can be defined, alternative representations should be used, based on interval analysis, probability boxes (p-boxes, see Section 2.2.4), evidence theory (Dempster-Shafer theory) (Shafer, 1976; L. A. Zadeh, 1996), possibility theory (see section 2.2.3), fuzzy sets (L. Zadeh, 1965) etc. Usually, the approach is to work with bounds on probability.

Many setups also contain a mixture of aleatory and epistemic uncertainty, which often takes the form that the researcher knows that there will be aleatory uncertainty but not its precise distribution. In these cases, a two-tiered (hierarchical) approach might be appropriate, where uncertainty is represented as a distribution of probability distributions. The “inner” probability distributions represent the aleatory uncertainty, whereas the outer distributions represent the researcher’s uncertainty about which is the correct one. If the outer distribution is chosen to be a probability distribution as well, we get a Bayesian setting. This is mostly done in a parametric way, where a family of feasible probability distributions is chosen which is parameterised by some real number ϑ (or a vector of such parameters). Then, a probability distribution for ϑ is given to represent epistemic uncertainty.

2.2.3 Possibility Theory

Another approach is given by possibility theory (Dubois & Prade, 2001). Here, instead of a probability distribution, a possibility distribution is used to represent its uncertainty. This is a function π where $\pi(\vartheta) \in [0, 1]$ for each ϑ in the range Θ . This function is then extended to sets $E \subseteq \Theta$ via $\pi(E) = \sup_{\vartheta \in E} \pi(\vartheta)$. Expressing $\pi(E) = 0$ indicates that the parameter values in E are considered impossible, whereas $\pi(E) = 1$ implies that at least one value in E is completely possible. A possibility measure of 1 is a weaker statement compared to a probability of 1, as the possibilistic unit value states that the occurrence of an event is possible, whereas a probability of 1 states that the event is certain (certainty of an event in possibility theory would instead be expressed by setting the possibility of its complementary event to 0). This representation of uncertainty is particularly helpful when the available data is scarce or when based mostly on experts’ opinions, only the upper and lower bounds can be defined (e.g., uniform, triangular, trapezoidal distributions).

According to possibility theory, the probability of the uncertain variable being within a given interval can be bounded by a lower and upper value, based on measures of the possibility distribution function. It is possible thus to transform a possibility distribution function into a family of probability distributions bounded by limiting cumulative distributions. Information on representing epistemic uncertainty with possibility theory and an example of application can be found in (Baraldi, Popescu, & Zio, 2010). Similar to the Bayesian setup, this can be used in a two-tiered approach where a family of probability distributions parameterised by some $\vartheta \in \Theta$ is selected, and Θ is then equipped with a possibility distribution (de Cooman & Walley, 2002).

2.2.4 Probability Boxes

Finally, probability boxes (p-boxes) give yet another approach for mixed aleatory-epistemic setups (Ferson, Kreinovich, Ginzburg, Myers, & Sentz, 2003). They are defined by lower and upper boundary curves, denoted by \underline{F}_X and \overline{F}_X , to the CDF of an uncertain variable X . For any value x of the input domain, the true, but unknown, value of the CDF lies within these bounds such that $\underline{F}_X(x) \leq F_X(x) \leq \overline{F}_X(x)$. A p-box represents an uncertain variable with an unknown distribution function within the boundary curves, or belonging to distribution function families, the parameters of which are known in intervals.

2.3 Uncertainty Quantification

UQ aims to measure the impact of disturbances in the input variables on the system output. Through a systematic approach, it takes into account the uncertainties of all the sources of uncertainty and how they are propagated through the complex process. The target of UP may include the evaluation of statistical moments of the output (e.g., mean and variance), of confidence intervals, or of the complete probability density function of the output.

Some approaches for UQ are described in the following. The analytical approach calculates the uncertainty based on a given mathematical description. The sampling approach uses methods of DoE to repeat experiments with varying parameterisation and analyse the changes in the results. SA helps to focus on the most relevant factors for UQ. The UP approach for simulation, considers not only the inputs and outputs of the simulation but propagates uncertainty structures through the simulation. Finally, a reference is given on how to propagate information backwards through the simulation, improving initial uncertain assumptions for parameter values.

2.3.1 Analytical Approach

If the problem has no ‘internal’ randomness the relation between the inputs $\mathbf{x} = \langle x_1, \dots, x_N \rangle$ and the output y (which we assume to be one-dimensional) can be written as a function f , i.e.

$$y = f(\mathbf{x}),$$

an analytical approach to uncertainty propagation can be considered. It requires that the derivative of f at the input \mathbf{x} can be computed (this can even be the case when giving an explicit expression for f is difficult; see the load-flow example in Section 4.5.2). Under the assumption that the uncertainties in the inputs x_i are given as normal distributions, the uncertainty of the output is a normal distribution as well. More explicitly, if each x_i is normally distributed around

\bar{x}_i with standard deviation σ_{x_i} , the result is a normal distribution around $\bar{y} = f(\bar{x}_1, \dots, \bar{x}_N)$, where the standard deviation σ_y is given by the Root of Summed Squares (RSS) law (Deardorff, 2000):

$$\sigma_y = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial y}{\partial x_1}\right)^2 \sigma_{x_1}^2 + \dots + \left(\frac{\partial y}{\partial x_N}\right)^2 \sigma_{x_N}^2}$$

See Section 4.5.2 for a derivation of this formula and an example, Section 5.3 for a use case that applies this method.

2.3.2 Sampling

For more complex use cases, the analytical approach cannot be used and sampling-based approaches are commonly used. This means that simulations or experiments are repeated with changing input values within predefined intervals. This is often combined with SA to determine the importance ranking of the individual input parameters according to their contribution to output uncertainty, see Section 2.3.3.

The set of possible input combinations is called the input space or design space. It is the N -dimensional space defined by the lower and upper bounds of each random design variable. In this context, a MC analysis based on a random sampling design is a mature methodology for uncertain problems, provided that information on the probability distributions of the input parameters is available. The MC way to perform uncertainty analysis is to sample values from the input space, and for each sample point to evaluate the output value of the model, in order to produce a number of output values to be analysed statistically. However, the slow convergence of the process necessitates a large number of model evaluations, which may be impractical for time-consuming models. Experimental design is an effective method to maximise the amount of information gained by appropriately choosing a limited number of samples from the design space.

When all uncertainties are represented by probability functions, MC simulation is usually utilised for the UP. The MC simulation is based on random sampling (or rather, pseudo-random sampling, as the random numbers are generated by an algorithm aiming to resemble a true random process) and is outlined in the following:

For the input parameter X_1 of the input vector X , a value x_1^1 is sampled randomly according to its probability distribution. (Here, the superscript indicates the number of the sample, whereas the subscript indicates the index of the parameter in the input vector.) Similarly, for the other input parameters, values x_2^1, \dots, x_N^1 are randomly sampled according to the distribution of each input parameter. It is assumed that the parameters are independent of each other. (This contains the hidden assumption that the parameters are stochastically independent.) The vector $\mathbf{x}^1 = \langle x_1^1, \dots, x_N^1 \rangle$ is the first input sample point from the N -dimensional input space.

Repeating the process, a total of K points are randomly sampled, following the distributions of each input parameter.

For each input sample point $\mathbf{x}^k = \langle x_1^k, \dots, x_N^k \rangle$, $k = 1, 2, \dots, K$, the model is evaluated to produce a set of K model outputs $y^k = f(x_1^k, \dots, x_N^k)$, $k = 1, 2, \dots, K$. These output values can be used for statistical analysis.

There are cases where sampling the distributions directly is not possible. Commonly, this occurs with multidimensional distributions where the assumption that the different coordinates are independent is not justified. In these cases, one can sometimes use the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm (Metropolis, Rosenbluth, Rosenbluth, Teller, & Teller, 2004) or Gibbs sampling (Geman

& Geman, 1984). Both of these approaches fall under the term “Markov Chain Monte Carlo” sampling, where the idea is to set up a Markov Chain with easier-to-sample transition distributions which have the desired distribution as its stationary distribution (Geyer, 2011).

When uncertainties are modelled by alternative non-probabilistic representations (epistemic uncertainties), other approaches, based mostly on interval analysis, are utilised for UP. For example, for the propagation of input uncertainties that are modelled as p-boxes, the p-box of the response variable is traditionally estimated by a slicing algorithm in combination with interval analysis. The slicing algorithm transforms the propagation of p-boxes into the propagation of a large number of intervals (Zhang et al., 2020).

Alternatively, when both probabilistic and non-probabilistic representations of the input parameters are present, a procedure consisting of two nested loops may be followed. According to this approach, an outer loop performs a MC sampling for the aleatory parameters (represented by PDFs), while for each iteration an inner loop handles the epistemic parameters. An example of the application of the nested approach on the problem of uncertain power flow of an electrical power system can be found in (Aien, Rashidinejad, & Fotuhi-Firuzabad, 2014). Of course, this procedure – due to the nested loops – causes a large increase in the computational cost, and alternative approaches (e.g., surrogate models) may be preferential.

Another approach for overcoming the difficulty of expensive evaluations of the output of a model or system is through a surrogate model (often called meta-model or response surface method). A surrogate model is an easy-to-evaluate mathematical function that approximates the true function $y = f(\mathbf{x})$ of a complex process, based on pairs of input-output samples. A relatively small number of evaluations is performed in order to produce the set of pairs required to train the model. Following this, the approximation can be used for UP or SA calculations, with a cheap computational cost. There are several types of models that are widely used and have received sustained attention from researchers: Polynomial Chaos Expansions (PCEs), kriging (also known as Gaussian process modelling), Reduced-Order Model (ROM), and Artificial Neural Network (ANN).

2.3.3 Sensitivity Analysis

UP and SA share many common concepts and computational tasks. The first and one of the most significant steps of the forward process is the identification of uncertainty sources and their characterisation, i.e., the mathematical representation of the uncertainty (see Section 2.2). This uncertainty may arise from many sources, e.g., uncertainty in the correct values of the inputs \mathbf{x} , uncertainty about the correctness of the model f in representing the real-world system, observational errors, etc.

Many techniques of sampling based on experimental design are particularly useful for tasks of SA. For example, screening of input factors is a useful technique, aiming to discover those factors that have a substantive impact on the response of a model or system, with a relatively low computational effort. Typical screening designs are One (factor)-at-a-Time (OAT) experiments, in which the impact of changing the values of each of the chosen factors is evaluated in turn between consecutive evaluations, starting from an initial base value of the input vector. This design requires much fewer evaluations of the model or system, compared to a full factorial design where all possible combinations of the considered values of input factors are evaluated. As a preliminary analysis, this can effectively save time and effort by identifying the non-influential factors and ignoring their effect on response variability in the subsequent analysis.

For further investigation of the sensitivities of parameters, one wants to know which parameters

have the most effect on the outputs. A helpful method for this sensitivity analysis are Sobol indices, which compare the effects (Sobol, 2001; Saltelli, 2002; Saltelli et al., 2010).

As in (Saltelli et al., 2010), for any random variable Z depending on the factors X_1, \dots, X_k , we denote by $E_{X_i}(Z)$ and $V_{X_i}(Z)$ the mean and variance of Z over X_i (this will then be a random variable depending on the remaining factors) and by $E_{X_{\sim i}}(Z)$ and $V_{X_{\sim i}}(Z)$ the mean and variance of Z overall variable except for X_i (this will be a random variable depending on X_i).

For our model $Y = f(X_1, \dots, X_k)$, the sensitivity measure S_i is then defined as

$$S_i = \frac{V_{X_i}(E_{X_{\sim i}}(Y|X_i))}{V(Y)}, \quad (1)$$

which means the mean of Y is calculated for all possible values of $X_{\sim i}$ keeping X_i fixed ($E_{X_{\sim i}}(Y|X_i)$). The variance V_{X_i} is calculated over all possible values of X_i . In other words, the variance when varying the factor X_i of the mean of the model output when varying all other factors is taken to indicate the effect a change of the factor X_i has on the output. The value is divided by $V(Y)$ to normalise the index so that $0 \leq S_i \leq 1$.

While S_i measures the effect of varying X_i alone, the total effect index S_{Ti} also measures the higher order effects from interactions with other factors and is defined as

$$S_{Ti} = \frac{E_{X_{\sim i}}(V_{X_i}(Y|X_{\sim i}))}{V(Y)} = 1 - \frac{V_{X_{\sim i}}(E_{X_i}(Y|X_{\sim i}))}{V(Y)}, \quad (2)$$

which means the variance of Y is calculated for a fixed X_i over all possible factors $X_{\sim i}$ but X_i ($V_{X_i}(Y|X_{\sim i})$). The mean of the variance for all possible factors $X_{\sim i}$ but X_i is calculated.

More approaches for SA can be found in (Pianosi et al., 2016).

2.3.4 Uncertainty Propagation Approach

For large and complex CPES simulation experiments, the benefit of the sampling approach might be limited, as it is based on multiple executions of the simulation, which can be problematic with increasing execution time. Thus, a quite novel approach for UQ is presented here, which does not consider only the inputs and outputs of the simulation, but also the uncertainties within the simulation. Steinbrink proposed the ensemble-based “non-intrusive uncertainty quantification system for modular smart grid co-simulation” (Steinbrink, 2017) and also implemented it as a prototype for the co-simulation framework mosaik under the name MoReSQUE³. Thus, it is relevant in the context of ERIGrid 2.0, where example scenarios were created based on mosaik .

The described UQ process starts with the uncertainty assessment, which is similar as described in the two previous Sections 2.1 and 2.2. The two important aims of the assessment are the identification of uncertainty sources and the association of these with a suitable mathematical representation, on which the following UP is based. The uncertainty representations shown in Figure 3 are described in (Steinbrink, 2017). Of these, interval, distribution, and p-box are part of the implementation as so-called uncertainty structures. Distributions are represented by CDFs.

The UP itself is based on simulation components and not full scenarios. For the propagation, ensembles are used, which are replacing single simulation model entities with multiple entities

³<https://gitlab.com/mosaik/tools/mosaik-moresque>

as visualised in Figure 5. Each ensemble contains an input and output module, which does sampling based on the uncertainty structure at the input and creates a new uncertainty structure as output. Thus, different values from the uncertainty space can be calculated and the outputs used as input for the next simulation component.

To make uncertainty structures available for storing or analysis, MoReSQUE contains an Output Aggregation Module (OAM). This module transforms the internal uncertainty structure to minimum and maximum values for interval structures or mean, variance, and quantiles for distribution and p-box structures.

Figure 5: Schematic comparison of a mosaik scenario with a MoReSQUE scenario (Steinbrink, 2017).

The MoReSQUE approach and implementation is an important step towards UQ in co-simulation but is still having limitations. One important limitation is the non-existence of states and stochasticity in the simulation components, which drastically reduces the potential use cases for complex CPES scenarios. But as shown in the evaluation, compared to a MC sampling approach, MoReSQUE can achieve higher accuracy with a smaller sample size (Steinbrink, 2017, p.128ff.).

2.3.5 Backward Process

Occasionally, a computational model for a simulation is known (or chosen), but it contains parameters which need to be calibrated to the specific instance at hand. In this case, observations from the real-world system modelled by the simulation can be used to improve knowledge about the parameter values, provided such observations are available. This is called the backward process.

The way this is usually done involves a Bayesian setup, i.e. the aleatory uncertainties are modelled using probability distributions with parameters whose exact values are unknown. The current best guess for the parameters is encoded in the probability distribution, the so-called prior distribution, initially based on expert knowledge. Based on the agreement between the simulation and the real-world observations, the prior distribution is refined using Bayesian updates. More information on this framework can be found in (Kennedy & O'Hagan, 2001).

3 Process and Tools

Based on the foundations of UQ introduced in the previous section, this section aims to show how processes for the planning of experiments and tools for SA and UQ can be used for handling uncertainties and can be integrated into a workflow to achieve improved reproducibility. A process for the “Identification and Classification of Uncertainties” based on the HTD developed in ERIGrid and extended in this research regarding uncertainties is shown in Section 3.1. Section 3.2 introduces a toolbox using DoE approaches, which can be used for SA and UQ.

3.1 Identification and Classification of Uncertainties

An important step to support the reproducibility of experiments is a well-documented experiment design. With regard to working with experimental uncertainty, structured analysis, and documentation of the uncertainties identified and considered during the experiment design are probably as important as the uncertainties reported and quantified in the final experiment.

For the existing HTD, which offers a process and templates to structure the conceptual planning and specifications of an experiment, extensions were developed to support the structured identification and classification of uncertainties throughout the experiment planning phase. This section presents the identification of uncertainty aspects using HTD and the extensions for detailed uncertainty classification.

3.1.1 Identification of Uncertainties using the HTD approach

The original HTD process, referred in Section 2.1.2, already elicited information related to uncertainty aspects relevant to all three levels of the HTD. However, these aspects were of a shallow structure and did not facilitate a structured uncertainty analysis. In a preparatory phase, to prepare the data before the actual execution of the test procedure, the following steps are crucial for the process of UQ:

- Definition of the goals of the experiment. The planning of the experiment is based on the careful consideration of the defined purpose of the experiment.
- Identification of the outputs, the quantities of interest. The outputs of the complex process, to be measured or calculated, have to be clear and well-defined beforehand, as they are important for the final conclusions.
- Identification of the sources of uncertainty. The sources of uncertainty have to be identified a priori. Uncertainties may arise from several sources, including uncertainty in inputs (e.g., parameters, initial conditions, boundary conditions etc.), model inadequacy due to the difference between a model and the true system, etc.
- Characterisation of the uncertainty of the inputs. The following step is the mathematical representation of the uncertainty of the selected inputs. Most frequently the PDF or the intervals of variation of the inputs will have to be identified. This task is based mostly on expert knowledge, experimental data, and a literature survey. Typically, the inputs are characterised in terms of PDFs, as this allows for a probabilistic approach of the UP, based e.g., on random sampling and MC analysis. However, in many cases, there is not enough knowledge and information on the PDFs of the inputs, especially for the epistemic type of uncertainties. In such cases, alternative representations may be required, based on interval analysis, fuzzy intervals, p-boxes, etc. Other information which might affect

the next steps of the UQ procedure should be included at this phase, for example, the correlation among specific inputs.

After these steps, UQ processes may follow as, e.g., UP, to determine statistical moments or complete probability distribution of output, based on the uncertainties of the parameters, and their propagation through the complex process under investigation.

The aforementioned steps are well in line with the HTD process and can be integrated into it. The early definition of the goals of an experiment and the identification of the outputs of interest, foreseen at the TC level, are important. Further assistance is provided by the guidelines and a supporting template file (Microsoft Office Excel type file), for the identification of the sources of uncertainty and their classification. The procedure for the identification can be distinguished in the following viewpoint cases.

System Configuration (SC) and Use Case (UC)

Following the definition of the SC, which has already been specified at the TC level, the procedure for the identification of sources of uncertainty is facilitated. The sources of uncertainty are explored by examining the system components, one by one, and identifying the parameters that may potentially disturb the output of the system, based on the experience and knowledge of the practitioner. For complex systems, an extension of the HTD was suggested, by utilising an appended template for SC, based on the PreCISE approach (Widl et al., 2019) developed in the EU SMILES project⁴.

This appended template includes a SBD representation, which provides an organised overview of all components that constitute the SC and may offer further facilitation. All elements in a SBD representation are conceptualised as classes and organised on different branches of a tree to reflect different domains and levels of detail. An example of such a representation is available on the first sheet of the supporting Microsoft Office Excel template file (see Figure 6). The identified parameters are characterised with the aid of a set of predefined taxonomy terms. The final outcome of this process, under the SC viewpoint, aims to cover the identification of the variable attributes of the TC level of the HTD (see Figures 7a and 7b).

Figure 6: System Breakdown (SBD) part of template for uncertainty in HTD.

⁴<https://www.ecria-smiles.eu/project>

Component		Parameter Name	Unit	Default Value	Type of uncertainty	Randomness or Lack of Knowledge/Data? <i>(automatic suggestion)</i>	Uncertainty Representation Type	Short explanation
Name	SC Subsystem							
					Uncertain parameter	epistemic and aleatory	Set	
					model (structure) uncertainty	epistemic		
						#NV		
						#NV		
						#NV		
						#NV		
						#NV		
						#NV		

(a) First part of the SC and UC part of template for uncertainty in HTD

Component		Potential factor?	Factor in sensitivity screening?	Factor ranking	Mapping	Target	Target 2 (for trade-off analysis)	Target 3 (for trade-off analysis)
Name	SC Subsystem							
		X	X	level (1... 3)	Range of parameter values or deviation from default value	Target Metric X		

(b) Second part of the SC and UC part of template for uncertainty in HTD.

Figure 7: SC and UC part of template for uncertainty in HTD.

Purpose of Investigation (Pol)

Depending on the defined Pol, specific points of the identification process are emphasised. The viewpoint differentiates depending on the specific objective of interest, in terms of uncertainty analysis, sensitivity analysis or scaling analysis (see Figure 8).

Potential Pol	Type of Uncertainty/sensitivity/scaling effect	Short explanation	Target Metric	Formula	Parameter for Target	Parameter for Target	Parameter for Target	Factors in screening	Ranked factors
Characterization ...	uncertainty	The objective is to investigate if these parameters introduce substantial uncertainties in the system's behaviour/end results.	Target Metric X		dropdown parameter from SC and UC	dropdown parameter from SC and UC	dropdown parameter from SC and UC	look up from SC and UC sheet	look up from SC and UC sheet
Characterization ...	sensitivity	The objective is systematically to change the parameters of the complex process to determine the effects of such changes on its output.							
Characterization ...	scaling effect	Aspects that are different when the benchmark is scaled up and deserve special analysis.							
interactions of multiple parallel controlled units									

Figure 8: Pol part of template for uncertainty in HTD.

Experiment Specification (ES)

During the HTD consideration at the ES phase, it is identified how the TS is implemented in a given RI. At this level of the HTD procedure detailing, some new uncertainties are introduced, related to the specific means of the implementation of the test via the setup of the given RI, which could not have been identified at the previous levels. The means of implementation concern for example the utilisation of software models, co-simulation, real-time digital simulators, hardware equipment, interconnection of multiple laboratories etc. As a guideline, in the supporting template, a drop-down list was populated with all the possible combinations of 'setups',

and the corresponding sources of uncertainty was identified and displayed for each item of the list (see Figure 9). These suggested sources of uncertainty may be transferred to the ES Template of the HTD. Any other actions aiming to mitigate the overall output uncertainty may also be reported at this phase.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1	Name	Experiment Setup Type	Representational Uncertainty	Short explanation	Other Type of RI Uncertainty	Short explanation	Precision of equipment	Measurement Uncertainty
2		Pure simulation/monolithic/single RI	Model accuracy Type of simulation (EMT vs RMS vs Power Flow)	Add your own text	Simulator Limitations Computational capacity	Add your own text		
3								
4								
5								
6								
7								
8								
9								

Figure 9: ES part of template for uncertainty in HTD.

3.1.2 Classification of Uncertainty Types

Different types of uncertainty were introduced in Section 2.1.1. The classification of uncertainty sources can help to handle them correctly. Especially, the differentiation between aleatory and epistemic uncertainty is often helpful. It might indicate already the type of uncertainty representation, as aleatory uncertainty is commonly represented by distributions, while epistemic uncertainty is often represented by intervals.

Based on the type of uncertainty, also the representation of uncertainty can be chosen in the template (see Figure 7a). Different types of uncertainty representation were introduced in Section 2.2, an overview is depicted in Figure 3. The most common representations of uncertainty are probably intervals and distributions. Other representations are P-Box, Set, Fuzzy Set, Fuzzy Interval, Dempster-Shafer Structure (DSS), and Random Fuzzy Variables (RFV).

3.2 Toolbox for Sensitivity Analysis and Uncertainty Quantification

The toolbox is based on preliminary work of a summer school, which was part of the ERI-Grid project (*ERIGrid/NA4-SummerSchool-DTU-2018: v2.0*, n.d.). It allows to use different DoE methods for SA and UQ of simulation scenarios. In ERIGrid 2.0 it was extended under this activity with more statistical methods and was integrated with a more complex simulation scenario as shown in Section 5.1. In addition to the DoE approaches, the toolbox provides a data structure to define the parameters of a simulation and foster the reproducibility of an experiment.

3.2.1 Toolbox Overview

The toolbox is divided into three main parts which are explained below. An illustration of the toolbox structure and its associated processes is shown in Figure 10.

The first part consists of a toolbox for the definition of simulation parameterisation and inputs that enclose three main processes. An initial process is the definition of basic scenario configuration with the values for the parameters that describe the model of the system to be simulated. Subsequently, it follows the process in which the definition of the factors, their variations and

Figure 10: Flowchart of the developed toolbox for sensitivity analysis and uncertainty quantification.

target metrics is done. The factors are the parameters, which will be varied between the different simulation runs, and their variations can be defined as intervals or distributions depending on the chosen sampling method.

In the end, a sampling process is carried out in which a set of value combinations are generated according to the parameter variation ranges defined in previous stages. These parameterisations for multiple simulation runs are called recipes and are stored in a data structure to be used as input for the simulation.

In the examples, the mosaik co-simulation framework is used for simulation, which is called directly with the previously defined recipes. But the toolbox is not limited to specific software and could also be used with other simulation tools or even hardware laboratory experiments as the recipes are provided as JSON data.

Once the simulation framework receives the data with the different parameterisations generated in the previous step, it proceeds to introduce the variables' values into the model to calculate the system response. The outcomes of the simulation will depend on the modelled system.

In the last step of the process, the results from the simulation are used as input in the Toolbox for analysis which implements statistical methods (e.g., ANOVA) to analyse the effects of the response of the system modelled with respect to variations in the input parameters.

Additionally, the toolbox visualises the relation between input and output variations through plots that are configurable by the user. In the following lines, the process carried out within each toolbox will be explained in more detail.

3.2.2 Definition of Simulation Parameterisation and Inputs

The part of the toolbox for the definition of simulation parameters and inputs generates the recipes for multiple simulation runs with varied parameterisation. Based on the recipes the simulators and respective entities are initialised.

In the JSON file, the value for each simulation parameter (e.g., scenario name or step size) is specified individually. Additionally, it must be included the "basic configuration" parameters which are sorted as a dictionary. These parameters set the values for the variables associated with the system modelled. For instance, in the Multi-Energy Network model, the basic configuration parameters stand for hot water tank dimensions (height, diameter), the delta of control voltage for the heat pump, and other set points.

The parameters which are included in the JSON file are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1: Input parameters overview for the Toolbox for the definition of simulation parameterisation.

Parameter	Definition	Value Type
samples	Number of samples to be considered in the sampling method	integer
doe_type	Determine the method used for sampling and analysis (see Table 2 for possible values)	string
add_extreme_points	Adds minimum and maximum values of ranges to variations (only effective for sobol doe_type)	boolean
parallelize	if the simulation scenario allows it, multiple simulation runs can be executed in parallel	boolean
num_processes	maximum number of processes executed simultaneously during the simulation (depending on the machine cores)	integer
skip_simulation	If only the analysis script should be run with already existing simulation results, simulation can be skipped	boolean
summary_filename	Name of the file in which the values of target metrics for the different simulation runs will be stored	string
drop_first_day_data	The first day of simulation of the ME benchmark can be dropped as it might contain unwanted initialisation behaviour (van der Meer et al., 2022)	boolean
plots	Enables the storage of the images after the simulation is finished	boolean
dpi	Sets the "dots per inch" parameter of the images produced by the simulation	integer
show_plots	Determine whether the plots are displayed in a window or not, once the simulation run is completed	boolean
format	Image format of the results graphics (e.g., png, jpeg)	string
folder_figures	Name of the folder that will contain the graphics resultant from the analysis	string
basic_conf	Dictionary which contains the simulation settings such as the scenario name and ID	dictionary
target_metrics	The target metrics which should be used for analysis	list
variations_dict	Contains each of the parameters that are variable (i.e., factors) and will be considered as dependent as well as their variation ranges (specifically the lower and upper limits or distribution).	dictionary
entities_parameters	Parameterisation for all models of the simulation (specific for the simulation scenario)	dictionary

3.2.3 Analysis

The analysis component is composed of a set of functions addressed to process the data and perform the statistical analysis including methods such as meta-modelling, ANOVA, Sobol indices, or extended Fourier Amplitude Sensitivity Test (eFAST) (cf. Table 2). Functions to plot analysis results are also included.

This part of the toolbox receives the configuration parameters (i.e., JSON file) and the simula-

tion results as input. In the first step, the target metrics are calculated based on the simulation results. This step is specific to the simulation scenario. In the examples a HDF5 file-based database is used to store the simulation results and also the summarised target metrics. But this part could also be replaced by other databases or types of files.

In the second step, the calculated target metrics are used for the chosen statistical method for analysis of the simulation outcomes. Most of the methods have also some plotting functions included to visualise the results.

Table 2: Overview of the sampling and analysis methods in the toolbox.

String	Sampling Method	Analysis Method
sobol	Sobol sequence	meta model
extreme_points	Minimum and maximum values of interval	ANOVA
LHS	LHS	meta model
sobol_indices	Sobol indices sampling (Saltelli et al., 2010)	sobol indices
fast	eFAST sampling (Saltelli et al., 1999)	fast

4 Guidelines

After the explanation of the foundations of UQ and the description of tools and processes, this section aims to give practical guidelines on how to choose the right approach or tool to answer the previously defined relevant questions. The different approaches are characterised and explained with examples.

4.1 Educational Example Case

The following setting is used as a basic example to describe the approaches. It represents an input or measurement uncertainty case with fluctuating production or consumption of a simulated energy system. The following effects are considered: The system contains a PV system, which calculates its power based on the DNI and can be parameterised. In the first step uncertainty in the DNI input data is expected and the effect on the output power is investigated.

As a more relevant example use case, in a second step, a load flow calculation is added to look at the output voltage values. The mathematical background for both cases is shown in the next sections.

PV System

We will use a simplified calculation for a PV system which considers only the direct component of the irradiance. For more precise results, one should also take the diffuse and reflected irradiance into consideration. However, the simplified version is enough to demonstrate the approach and keeps the formulas more manageable.

Therefore, we consider the power output of a PV system to be given by

$$P = AeN_D,$$

where A is the area of the panel, e is its efficiency and N_D is the part of the irradiance which is normal to the panel. This, in turn, may be calculated as:

$$N_D = D \cos \iota,$$

where D is the direct normal irradiance and ι is the incidence angle, namely:

$$\iota = \arccos(\cos \varphi \cdot \cos(\alpha - \alpha_{\text{tilt}}) \cdot \sin \varphi_{\text{tilt}} + \sin \varphi \cdot \cos \varphi_{\text{tilt}}).$$

Here, α and φ are the azimuth and elevation of the sun, α_{tilt} and φ_{tilt} describe the setup of the solar panel. Finally, α and φ can be computed from the current time and the location of the solar panel as:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha &= \text{atan2}(\sin \tau, \sin \Phi \cdot \cos \tau - \cos \Phi \cdot \tan \delta), \\ \phi &= \arcsin(\cos \Phi \cdot \cos \delta \cdot \cos \tau + \sin \Phi \cdot \sin \delta), \end{aligned}$$

where τ is the solar hour angle (such that solar noon is 0°), Φ is the latitude of the panel's location and δ is an approximate calculation of the declination of the sun, i.e.,

$$\delta = 23.45^\circ \cdot \sin(2\pi(d - 81)/365)$$

where d is the day of the year ($\text{atan2}(y, x)$ is the usual two-argument function giving the (signed) angle of the vector (x, y) with the x -axis).

In this example, the DNI and the setup parameters of the solar panel (α_{tilt} and φ_{tilt}) would be typically uncertain, with the setup parameters being examples of parametric uncertainty, as they do not change over time (whereas the true value of the DNI can fall differently in relation to its estimated value at each time step). The latitude might also be uncertain, but it will usually be known to a reasonable accuracy, so no significant errors will be introduced by considering it as certain. As for the type of uncertainty, that depends on the available data. For example, it seems reasonable to assume that over time, one will learn how accurate the setup of solar panels usually is, turning the setup parameters into aleatory uncertainty. The right modelling of DNI depends on the quality of the available weather forecast.

Load Flow

As a second example, we consider the load flow for a system with three buses, numbered 0, 1, and 2. Bus 0 is the slack bus where voltage angle ϑ_0 and voltage magnitude $|V_0|$ are fixed. Bus 1 is a load bus where real and reactive power P_1 and P_2 are fixed. Bus 2 is a generator bus where real power P_2 and voltage magnitude $|V_2|$ are fixed. Also, the admittance between the buses is given in the form of the (complex) 3×3 admittance matrix $Y_{\text{BUS}} = G + jB$ (we number the rows and columns starting with 0, so they agree with the bus indices).

The real and reactive power P_0 , Q_0 at the slack bus, the voltage angle and voltage magnitude ϑ_1 , $|V_1|$ at the load bus, and the voltage angle and reactive power ϑ_2 , Q_2 at the generator bus are the unknown factors in this problem.

Load-flow problems like this occur frequently in energy systems.

Combined System

Finally, the two basic examples may also be combined by using the PV system from the first example as the generator or load (depending on whether one controls the corresponding voltage magnitude or reactive power) in the load-flow system.

4.2 Typical Uncertainty Questions for Experiment Design

To aid researchers in their experimental design concerning UQ, we propose a set of stereotypical research questions. Each question is associated with a different understanding of uncertainty in an experiment and leads to different methods.

To use this guideline, the experiment planner needs to identify which of the questions most closely matches their need for quantifying uncertainty aspects.

4.2.1 What is the effective uncertainty of the experimental outcome?

How can the uncertainty of the ‘main outcomes’ be quantified?

To apply uncertainty analysis, one first needs a value to apply uncertainty analysis. In the context of these guidelines, this will always be a real-valued variable. If the experiment has several such outcomes, UQ can be applied to each of them individually. However, if the outcome is more complicated (say a function, as the solution of a differential equation would be), it first needs to be aggregated into a single value (for example, by integrating, or by evaluating at a

suitably chosen point). Which method is appropriate for this aggregation depends on the experiment in question and the selection is therefore down to the experimenter's experience. In the context of HTD, the method of aggregation should be part of the test description.

Having selected a value for the analysis, one needs to choose an appropriate UQ method. In these guidelines, we propose the following options:

- If the relation between the inputs and the output is non-random, the uncertainties in the inputs are (roughly) normally distributed and the derivative of the function mapping inputs to outputs can be evaluated, the analytical approach gives tangible results, potentially without requiring many model evaluations.
- For problems with a limited number of input factors, a basic MC simulation can produce results quickly and reliably.
- In higher dimensional cases, other sampling methods should be used to reduce the necessary number of model evaluations by avoiding 'clumping' of the evaluated points and by concentrating on the areas of the sample space where the behaviour is most interesting.

For the basic example of the PV system, we will consider the DNI as an uncertain input and consider the effect on the produced power. As a second step, we will also consider the setup of the PV system (given by α_{tilt} and φ_{tilt}) as uncertain, still taking the power as the output.

How can the uncertainty be systematically characterised?

When representing uncertainty as a single number, it is necessary to specify what this number represents. Often, it will be the standard deviation of the variable in question; however, even that is not a full specification for there are many distributions exhibiting any given standard deviation. To characterise uncertainty, one should therefore specify at least a probability distribution. When no such specification is made, usually the normal distribution is meant.

In more complicated cases involving epistemic uncertainty, one might also specify a distribution of probability distributions.

4.2.2 How can the uncertainty of the experimental outcome be reduced?

Which uncertain input parameter is dominant and introduces the most uncertainty on the outputs?

In order to reduce the uncertainty, it makes sense to concentrate efforts on those factors that introduce the most uncertainty. To this end, these factors need to be identified. Here, the techniques of ANOVA and Sobol indices can be useful.

How can the uncertainty be further reduced (if possible)?

As discussed before, uncertainty can be roughly divided into aleatory (i.e., random) and epistemic (i.e., knowledge-based) uncertainty. If the uncertainty is due to truly random and non-measurable factors, there is a lower limit to the uncertainty that can not be undercut. However, epistemic uncertainty can be reduced by gaining a better understanding of the underlying system. In doing so, internal factors of the experiments, previously considered as random, turn into input factors that can be controlled or at least measured (so their influence can be quantified by comparing their value and the outputs over many experiment runs).

4.2.3 How can the representational uncertainty of a simulation-based test setup be characterised and accounted for?

How can the representational uncertainty of a computational test setup with respect to physical ground truth (real-world or laboratory) be characterised?

To reduce costs and improve performance, laboratory experiments are often modelled and executed as simulations, which might lead to representational uncertainties. It is the uncertainty that arises from the fact that a simulation can never reflect reality flawlessly. So representational uncertainty can be due to deliberate or accidental simplifications in the models chosen to represent the real world, due to rounding errors in the computations, or simply due to software bugs. To characterise this representational uncertainty, system validation approaches for comparing the simulation results can be used.

In some cases, the SuT is modelled by a computational setup that can be adjusted using one or several parameters. These parameters will frequently be calibrated using the results from real-world runs of the experiments and one is then interested in determining the uncertainty in these parameter values.

How can I estimate the accuracy of my experimental results by propagating representational uncertainty of a computational model?

Having determined values for the parameters of a computational model, potentially with some uncertainty, one can then run the model on further inputs to extrapolate the effect of extrinsic uncertainty. One is then faced with the problem of quantifying the uncertainty in the computed outputs, stemming from the uncertainty in the parameter values.

4.3 Experiment Setup Uncertainties

To understand the uncertainties we have in our experiment, we assess also the experimental setup, which often is not fully deterministic. In the already mentioned types of uncertainty which are the same for software and hardware experiments, laboratory experiments can add more uncertainty issues, which are discussed in the following.

Noise Issues

For laboratory experiments, one always has to deal with noise issues, as the state of the real world can not be controlled or measured to 100%. Thus, one can have noise in the parameterisation of equipment or the inputs, caused by controlling an actuator that is not completely accurate. On the other side of an experiment, output noise for the measurement of real-world effects occurs.

Noise issues can be aleatory in the form of an additive noise, which can be caused by quantisation errors, for example. Epistemic forms of noise can be an offset or drift.

Uncertainty Issues – Lack of Knowledge

Other representational and epistemic uncertainty issues can be behavioural (e.g., “How does the actuator respond to a setpoint?”) or parametric uncertainty (e.g., “Does the lab grid have the same parameters as my model?”). These uncertainties are typically dealt with during the

first stages of an experiment, and in the case of validation, efforts have an important role in assessing the maturity level achieved by a solution during testing.

Intrinsic Uncertainty

The International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) Glossary defines this term as:

“Intrinsic uncertainty of the measurand minimum uncertainty that can be assigned in the description of a measured quantity. In theory, the intrinsic uncertainty of the measurand is obtained if the measurand is measured using a measurement system having a negligible measurement instrumentation uncertainty.” (IEC Glossary Entry, 2009)

A typical case of this uncertainty is the quality class of a measurement device, which can be composed of aleatory uncertainty, and potentially of a removable offset (epistemic uncertainty component).

Extrinsic Uncertainty

Extrinsic uncertainty is caused by effects which are not part of the experiment itself and cannot be controlled. For example, a laboratory experiment is always also part of its real environment and might be exposed to weather and temperature effects. Also, limited bandwidth and communication time delays have to be mentioned here, which would be extrinsic when a non-exclusive network is used, but can also be intrinsic if an exclusive network infrastructure is part of the experiment.

4.4 Guideline Overview

4.4.1 Approach Selection Criteria

Here we provide some criteria for the classification of uncertainty analysis, which should help to choose the right approach. In Table 3, the different approaches are listed and the selection criteria are indicated for which the approaches can be reasonable.

1. Character of the Uncertainty

- (a) *Extrinsic*: Extrinsic uncertainty refers to the uncertainties in the conditions under which the experiment is run. It usually cannot be controlled when running real-world experiments, however, it needs to be accounted for. Typically, one can try to characterise it, use blocking (i.e., form blocks of experiment runs with sufficiently similar conditions to analyse together), and plan around it (for example, by running the experiments at times where the conditions are most likely to be suitable). In simulations, the conditions can be set more freely; here, it is the uncertainty that is assigned to the input data. A typical example of this type of uncertainty is weather.
- (b) *Measurement*: All measurement devices have a specific amount of uncertainty within their measurement. For example, for system validation, it is important to know about this uncertainty to deal with it correctly. In simulation setups, there often is no measurement uncertainty, unless the measuring process is explicitly simulated as well (floating-point rounding errors could be considered measurement uncertainty, but they are usually small enough to be negligible).

- (c) *Other Intrinsic Uncertainty*: Intrinsic uncertainty is uncertainty that is actually part of the SuT. It is what remains after all extrinsic and measurement uncertainties have been accounted for and it usually cannot be reduced. Examples would be quantum effects or the precise distribution of time delays in a distributed lab experiment. In simulations, this uncertainty will often be implemented via random sampling in the simulation.

The characterisation of uncertainty is a matter of perspective, to some degree. For example, while testing a measuring device, its “measurement uncertainties” should be considered as intrinsic, instead.

Occasionally, what appears to be a single source of uncertainty should be considered as a mix of different uncertainties. Getting back to the distributed lab experiment, the mean and variance of the time delays in the communication system might depend strongly on the time at which the simulation is run, and might therefore be considered extrinsic. However, the delays of the individual messages would usually be considered intrinsic to the setup.

2. Form of the System under Test

The SuT might exist in different forms, and different approaches apply to each. The forms identified for these guidelines are

- (a) *Experimental Setup*: The system contains real-world components. This includes cases where simulation and real-world experiments are combined and many real-time simulations, especially where several simulations communicate over the internet (as the communication system should be considered a real-world component).
- (b) *Simulation*: A model of the SuT exists as a pure software implementation.
- (c) *Analytical Model*: The SuT is described through mathematical formulae so that analytical methods (like partial derivatives) can be applied. It is not always necessary that the outputs are expressed as functions of the inputs directly, see Section 4.5.2.

4.4.2 Selection of Approach

After identifying the type of research question and type of problem, the overview of approaches in Table 3 can support finding a suitable approach for handling uncertainty. The approaches are described in the following section and for further information, references to the appropriate subsections in the foundations and use cases are provided.

4.5 Methods and Approaches

The approaches for UQ listed in Table 3 are described in the following from a practical point of view with small examples of implementations. Additionally, requirements for using the approach and references to the description of the theoretical foundations of the approach and use cases using the approach are given.

4.5.1 Uncertainty Assessment and Categorisation

Uncertainty Assessment (UA) aims to identify and describe the initial uncertainties within the input data and system under consideration. Thus, it is usually helpful for answering if uncertainty

Table 3: Overview of approaches.

Approach	Question	Type of Problem	Requirements	Found. (Sec.)	Use Case (Sec.)
Uncertainty Assessment	II.b	all	Understanding of the use case, expert knowledge	2.1.1, 3.1	–
Analytical Approach	I.a	1a, 2c	Mathematical description of model is available	4.5.2	5.3
Sampling	I.a, I.b, II.a	1a, 1c, 1b, 2a, 2b	repeatable simulation/lab setup	2.1.1, 3.1	5.1, 5.2
MoReSQUE	I.a, I.b, III.b	1a, 1c, 2b	Detailed models are available	2.3	–
System Validation	III.a, III.b	1a, 1c, 1b, 2a, 2b	repeatable simulation/lab setup	4.5.5	–

might be reducible or not and addresses question II.b (cf. Table 4). The right representation of uncertainty has to be chosen, the type of uncertainty has to be described and the uncertainty quantified. This is usually done based on expert knowledge but might be supported by tools like SA to identify the most important factors.

Table 4: Uncertainty assessment, addressing question II.b.

Relevant uncertainty question type	Question II.b
For which type of problem is this approach useful?	all
What are the requirements to be usable?	Understanding of the use case, expert knowledge
Reference to use case/example	—
Where can I find the description of foundations/tools?	HTD process Section 3.1/uncertainty types Section 2.1.1

UA is usually the first step before a UQ is done. It can help to answer questions based on the type of uncertainty chosen. For example, the classification of uncertainties in aleatory or epistemic uncertainty can give help to decide if they can be reduced or not.

To improve reproducibility it is also important to document the assumptions taken at this phase. Thus, the Microsoft Office Excel template can support the user in this process as it described several steps to further define and document the uncertainties to be considered.

4.5.2 Analytical Approach

This approach can be used to estimate the uncertainty in the form of a number, thus answering question I.a (cf. Table 5), though it also shows which input uncertainty is most relevant to the output uncertainty. To apply it, an appropriate mathematical model must be available, namely, we need to be able to calculate the partial derivatives of the outputs with respect to the inputs (at the considered input vector). Note that it is not always necessary to be able to actually write down the outputs as a function of the inputs, see the load flow below for example.

To apply the analytical approach, we must make the following simplifying assumptions: there is a “true” value x of every measurement from which each measurement will differ by some error δx . We take this error to be a random variable and we make the assumption that it is normally

Table 5: Analytical approach, addressing question I.a.

What question can this approach answer?	Question I.a
For which type of problem is this approach useful?	1a, 2c
What are the requirements to be usable?	Mathematical description of model is available/possible
Reference to use case/example	DEMO2 (Section 5.3)
Where can I find the description of foundations/tools?	In the section below

distributed with a mean of 0; so its distribution is fully determined by the variance $\sigma_x^2 = \overline{\delta x^2}$ (a note on notation: δx^2 is to be understood as $(\delta x)^2$ and the overline indicates the expected value).

If x is adjusted by δx , the derivative gives us the approximation:

$$f(x + \delta x) \approx f(x) + \frac{df}{dx} \delta x,$$

or, denoting the resulting error in the output by δf ,

$$\delta f \approx \frac{df}{dx} \delta x.$$

The variance of the output f is:

$$\sigma_f^2 = \overline{\delta f^2} = \left(\frac{df}{dx} \right)^2 \overline{\delta x^2} = \left(\frac{df}{dx} \right)^2 \sigma_x^2,$$

and therefore:

$$\sigma_f = \left| \frac{df}{dx} \right| \sigma_x.$$

So the uncertainty scales by (absolute value of) the derivative of the function under consideration.

Let us now consider the case where f depends on two variables, x and y . Then,

$$\delta f \approx \frac{\partial f}{\partial x} \delta x + \frac{\partial f}{\partial y} \delta y.$$

The variance σ_f^2 is the mean of the squared error, i.e.

$$\sigma_f^2 = \overline{(\delta f)^2} \approx \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x} \right)^2 \overline{(\delta x)^2} + \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial y} \right)^2 \overline{(\delta y)^2} + \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x} \right) \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial y} \right) \overline{\delta x \delta y}.$$

If we assume that δx and δy are independent, then $\overline{\delta x \delta y} = \overline{\delta x} \cdot \overline{\delta y} = 0$, since $\overline{\delta x} = \overline{\delta y} = 0$ by our assumption that the errors are normally distributed with mean 0. Note that the similar simplification $\overline{\delta x^2} = \overline{\delta x}^2 (= 0)$ would not be valid, as δx is not independent of itself (except in trivial cases). Instead, $\overline{\delta x^2}$ is precisely the uncertainty σ_x^2 .

Whence we arrive at the root of RSS law (Deardorff, 2000),

$$\sigma_f = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x} \right)^2 \sigma_x^2 + \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial y} \right)^2 \sigma_y^2}.$$

This law also generalises to any (finite) number of independent variables.

Occasionally, it can be useful to consider the relative uncertainties $\frac{\sigma_f}{|f|}$, $\frac{\sigma_x}{|x|}$, and so on. This is due to their relationship to the logarithmic derivative $\frac{f'}{f}$ which plays nicer with products.

For example, if $f = x^k y^l$, then

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial x} = kx^{k-1}y^l \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial f}{\partial y} = lx^k y^{l-1},$$

and therefore

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\sigma_f^2}{f^2} &= \frac{1}{x^{2k}y^{2l}} \left(\left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x} \right)^2 \sigma_x^2 + \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial y} \right)^2 \sigma_y^2 \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{x^{2k}y^{2l}} \left(k^2 x^{2k-2} y^{2l} \sigma_x^2 + l^2 x^{2k} y^{2l-2} \sigma_y^2 \right) = k^2 \frac{\sigma_x^2}{x^2} + l^2 \frac{\sigma_y^2}{y^2}, \end{aligned}$$

which is nicer than the term for σ_f . (Deardorff, 2000) contains additional information on this approach.

PV System

We will consider the basic example of the PV system. For now, we will assume all variables except for the DNI D to be fixed. In that case, we can forego the calculation of the corresponding partial derivatives and we get the following propagation formula

$$\sigma_P = \left| \frac{dP}{dD} \right| \sigma_D = |Ae \cos \iota| \sigma_D.$$

Assuming a latitude of $\Phi = 32.117^\circ$, an area of $A = 1 \text{ m}^2$, an efficiency of $e = 0.2$, an elevation $\varphi_{\text{tilt}} = 45^\circ$ and azimuth of the solar panel of $\alpha_{\text{tilt}} = 0^\circ$ and a time of 14:00, i.e., $\tau = 30^\circ$, on the 144th day of the year ($d = 144$), we get (following the formulas from Section 4.1):

$$\delta = 20.73^\circ, \quad \alpha = 74.37^\circ, \quad \varphi = 60.95^\circ, \quad \iota = 44.71^\circ.$$

If our projected DNI is $D = 0.6 \text{ kW/m}^2$ with an uncertainty of $\sigma_D = 0.05 \text{ kW/m}^2$, we get a power of

$$P = AeD \cos \iota = 0.085 \text{ kW},$$

with an uncertainty of

$$\sigma_P = |Ae \cos \iota| \sigma_D = 0.0071 \text{ kW}.$$

As a second example, we will now consider the exact setup of the PV system (i.e. φ_{tilt} and α_{tilt}) to be uncertain. We get:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dP}{d\varphi_{\text{tilt}}} &= AeD(\cos \varphi \cdot \cos(\alpha - \alpha_{\text{tilt}}) \cdot \cos \varphi_{\text{tilt}} - \sin \varphi \cdot \sin \varphi_{\text{tilt}}) \\ \frac{dP}{d\alpha_{\text{tilt}}} &= AeD(\cos \varphi \cdot \sin(\alpha - \alpha_{\text{tilt}}) \cdot \sin \varphi_{\text{tilt}}) \end{aligned}$$

and therefore:

$$\sigma_P = \sqrt{\left(\frac{dP}{dD} \right)^2 \sigma_D^2 + \left(\frac{dP}{d\varphi_{\text{tilt}}} \right)^2 \sigma_{\varphi_{\text{tilt}}}^2 + \left(\frac{dP}{d\alpha_{\text{tilt}}} \right)^2 \sigma_{\alpha_{\text{tilt}}}^2}.$$

Using the same values as above, we get:

$$\frac{dP}{dD} = 0.1421 \text{ m}^2, \quad \frac{dP}{d\varphi_{\text{tilt}}} = -0.06308 \text{ kW}, \quad \frac{dP}{d\alpha_{\text{tilt}}} = 0.03968 \text{ kW}$$

If we assume an uncertainty in the DNI of $\sigma_D = 0.05 \text{ kW/m}^2$ (as before) and setup uncertainties of $\sigma_{\varphi_{\text{tilt}}} = 3^\circ$, $\sigma_{\alpha_{\text{tilt}}} = 3^\circ$, we now get:

$$\sigma_P = 0.0081 \text{ kW},$$

so our uncertainty in the power value has increased slightly (as we would expect, given that we added additional input uncertainty).

Load Flow

In this problem, we run into the additional challenge that the system of equations governing it (see below) usually cannot be solved for the unknowns. This also prevents direct computation of the partial derivatives required for the analytical approach. However, as we will see, we can compute the required values indirectly.

As a reminder, we have the slack bus 0 with given voltage angle ϑ_0 and voltage magnitude $|V_0|$, a load bus 1 with given real and reactive power P_1 and Q_1 , and a generator bus 2 with given real power P_2 and voltage magnitude $|V_2|$. The unknowns are the voltage angle ϑ_1 and voltage magnitude $|V_1|$ at the load bus, and the voltage angle ϑ_2 at the generator bus (from these, the power P_0 and the reactive powers Q_0 and Q_2 may be calculated afterwards). The relation between these variables is given by the relevant power balance equations:

$$\begin{aligned} P_1 &= |V_1||V_0|(G_{10} \cos \vartheta_{10} + B_{10} \sin \vartheta_{10}) \\ &\quad + |V_1|^2(G_{11} \cos \vartheta_{11} + B_{11} \sin \vartheta_{11}) \\ &\quad + |V_1||V_2|(G_{12} \cos \vartheta_{12} + B_{12} \sin \vartheta_{12}), \\ Q_1 &= |V_1||V_0|(G_{10} \sin \vartheta_{10} - B_{10} \cos \vartheta_{10}) \\ &\quad + |V_1|^2(G_{11} \cos \vartheta_{11} - B_{11} \sin \vartheta_{11}) \\ &\quad + |V_1||V_2|(G_{12} \cos \vartheta_{12} - B_{12} \sin \vartheta_{12}), \\ P_2 &= |V_2||V_0|(G_{20} \cos \vartheta_{20} + B_{20} \sin \vartheta_{20}) \\ &\quad + |V_2||V_1|(G_{21} \cos \vartheta_{21} + B_{21} \sin \vartheta_{21}) \\ &\quad + |V_2|^2(G_{22} \cos \vartheta_{22} + B_{22} \sin \vartheta_{22}), \end{aligned}$$

where $|V_i|$ is the voltage magnitude at bus i , ϑ_i is the voltage angle at bus i , and we write ϑ_{ij} for $\vartheta_i - \vartheta_j$.

Starting with an arbitrary guess for the values of the unknowns and considering P_1 , Q_1 , and P_2 as functions of them, we can calculate the Jacobian:

$$J = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial P_1}{\partial \theta_1} & \frac{\partial P_1}{\partial |V_1|} & \frac{\partial P_1}{\partial \theta_2} \\ \frac{\partial Q_1}{\partial \theta_1} & \frac{\partial Q_1}{\partial |V_1|} & \frac{\partial Q_1}{\partial \theta_2} \\ \frac{\partial P_2}{\partial \theta_1} & \frac{\partial P_2}{\partial |V_1|} & \frac{\partial P_2}{\partial \theta_2} \end{pmatrix},$$

which tells us the linear change in P_1 , Q_1 , and P_2 as the unknowns vary (around the current guess), i.e.

$$\begin{pmatrix} \Delta P_1 \\ \Delta Q_1 \\ \Delta P_2 \end{pmatrix} \approx J \begin{pmatrix} \Delta \theta_1 \\ \Delta |V_1| \\ \Delta \theta_2 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (3)$$

However, in our case, we do not know the changes in ϑ_1 , $|V_1|$, and ϑ_2 : these are the values we want to calculate. Instead, we can calculate the change that we want to achieve on the left-hand side, namely as the difference between the values for P_1 , Q_1 , and P_2 given by the problem description and their value based on the current guess for the unknowns using the equations above.

This turns (3) into a linear system of equations which can be solved for $\Delta\vartheta_1$, $\Delta|V_1|$, and $\Delta\vartheta_2$. Updating the current guess via

$$\begin{aligned}\vartheta_1 &\leftarrow \vartheta_1 + \Delta\vartheta_1, \\ |V_1| &\leftarrow |V_1| + \Delta|V_1|, \\ \vartheta_2 &\leftarrow \vartheta_2 + \Delta\vartheta_2,\end{aligned}$$

we get a better guess and can start the process anew. We repeat until the errors ΔP_1 , ΔQ_1 , and ΔP_2 are below some threshold.

While solving the system (3) by inverting J is generally not advisable, the inverse J^{-1} at the solution has a meaningful interpretation for us. Namely, it is the Jacobian of the (local) inverse to the balance equations, i.e

$$J^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial\vartheta_1}{\partial P_1} & \frac{\partial\vartheta_1}{\partial Q_1} & \frac{\partial\vartheta_1}{\partial P_2} \\ \frac{\partial|V_1|}{\partial P_1} & \frac{\partial|V_1|}{\partial Q_1} & \frac{\partial|V_1|}{\partial P_2} \\ \frac{\partial\vartheta_2}{\partial P_1} & \frac{\partial\vartheta_2}{\partial Q_1} & \frac{\partial\vartheta_2}{\partial P_2} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (4)$$

So instead of expressing the unknowns ϑ_1 , $|V_1|$, and ϑ_2 as functions of the givens P_1 , Q_1 , and P_2 directly (which in general will be very difficult or even impossible) and differentiating those functions, we can use the inverse of the much-easier-to-compute Jacobian J to get the partial derivatives that we need for our uncertainty analysis (the arrangement of the entries in this matrix depends on the order chosen for the givens and unknowns while setting up the matrix J above. Essentially, J is transposed and the “numerator” and “denominator” of each partial derivative are swapped). For example, using the entries of the first row of J^{-1} , we can calculate

$$\sigma_{\vartheta_1} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial\vartheta_1}{\partial P_1}\right)^2 \sigma_{P_1}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial\vartheta_1}{\partial Q_1}\right)^2 \sigma_{Q_1}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial\vartheta_1}{\partial P_2}\right)^2 \sigma_{P_2}^2},$$

and similarly for $|V_1|$ and ϑ_2 . This is why J^{-1} is also called the *sensitivity matrix*.

Many tools for load-flow calculations will enable you to extract J , J^{-1} , or the negative of these matrices at the end of the calculation.

4.5.3 Use Sampling for Uncertainty Quantification

In most cases, the systems under consideration in energy research are too complex to apply the analytical approach from the previous section. In these cases, sampling approaches are commonly employed. They base on the repeated execution of a simulation/experiment. Thus, the simulation or experiment has to allow this repeated execution of the scenario/setup. Sampling methods (cf. Table 6) can support answering the questions regarding uncertainty quantification (i.e., questions I.a and I.b) and sensitivity analysis (i.e., question II.a).

Table 6: Sampling approaches, addressing questions I.a, I.b, and II.a.

What question can this approach answer?	I.a, I.b, II.a
For which type of problem is this approach useful?	1a, 1c, 1b, 2a, 2b
What are the requirements to be usable?	(automatically) repeatable simulation/lab setup
Reference to use case/example	Sections 5.1 and 5.2
Where can I find the description of foundations/tools?	Section 2.3

Forward Estimation of Output Uncertainty based on Sampling of Input Uncertainties

The most basic version is MC simulation: for each input variable x_i , a sample is drawn according to its assumed probability distribution (or, in more interdependent cases, a joint sample (x_1, \dots, x_N) is drawn according to their joint distribution). Then, the model f may be evaluated to get a sample output:

$$y^{(1)} = f(x_1, \dots, x_N).$$

This is repeated several times, producing outputs $y^{(1)}, \dots, y^{(K)}$. The *sample mean*

$$\bar{y} = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K y^{(k)},$$

is taken to be the resulting value. The uncertainty is obtained from the *sample variance*

$$\sigma_y^2 = \frac{1}{K-1} \sum_{k=1}^K (y^{(k)} - \bar{y})^2.$$

The denominator $K - 1$ (instead of K) might be surprising at first, but consider that we would otherwise get a variance of 0 (indicating absolute certainty about the result) if $K = 1$ because in this case, $y^{(1)} = \bar{y}$.

The problem with the basic approach is that the variance only decreases slowly, so many model evaluations are needed, especially in systems with many input variables.

For more complex systems with multiple uncertainty dimensions, this basic sampling strategy can be quite inefficient as it focuses on the areas of the parameter space with the highest probability. Thus, other sampling methods might be better for these situations.

Sampling Methods

Purely random sampling tends to result in clumps: the sampled points are less uniformly distributed than one might expect. As it is often more useful to use inputs from different areas of the sampling space, sampling methods can be used which pick the points in a more directed way (Janssen, 2013). Using these sampling methods, the calculated means tend to converge toward the 'true' value more quickly. For a more detailed overview of sampling methods, also see (Giunta et al., 2003).

In *LHS*, each dimension of the sampling space is divided into the same number K of sections (McKay, Beckman, & Conover, 1979). Each section should have (roughly) the same probability in the probability distribution for the corresponding factor. Then, K sampling points are selected such that in each dimension, each sector is hit exactly once (in the two-dimensional case, this is akin to placing 8 rooks on a chess board such that no rook sees any other rook; here K is chosen to be 8).

Sobol sequences are another example of quasi-random sequences that can be used for sampling purposes, even though they were originally conceived for integral approximations (Sobol', 1967). While more tricky to understand than Latin Hypercube Sampling (LHS), they have the advantage that they can be extended. That means, the existing samples (and, importantly, their associated output values) can be reused when one decides that one wants to add additional samples based on the analysis of the existing ones. They are first defined for picking points uniformly from an n -dimensional unit hypercube. By applying the inverses of the CDFs to each coordinate, sampling from other distributions is possible (provided the inverses exist).

In Figure 11 sampling results for different approaches are visualised. The two upper plots show MC and LHS, which are both based on the normal distribution of the problem definition (see Listing 1) for two factors. Both lower plots show a uniform distribution based MC and Sobol Sequences. For the sampling, the same problem definition was used and the bounds were calculated based on the normal distribution.

Figure 11: Comparison of different sampling methods.

Listing 1: Problem definition for sampling shown in Figure 11.

```

1 | problem = ProblemSpec({'names': ['x1', 'x2'],
2 |                       'groups': None,
3 |                       'dists': ['norm', 'norm'],
4 |                       'bounds': [[1.0, 0.5], [2.0, 1]],
5 |                       })

```

PV System

For a better understanding of the sampling approach, in the following the basic example of a PV model (see Section 4.1) is shown. The full code of the examples with all needed imports, outputs and plotting of results is provided in the ERIGrid 2.0 repository⁵.

Firstly, the DNI is seen as uncertain with normal distribution and a mean of 0.6 kW and a standard deviation of 0.05 kW as shown in Listing 2. A PV model is used here for the calculation of the power based on 4096 samples for one specific moment in time. As a result, one gets a mean of 0.085 kW, a standard derivation of 0.0073 kW, which is comparable to the results with the analytical approach (see Section 4.5.2).

Listing 2: Sampling example with PV model and 1 factor.

```

1 | problem = ProblemSpec({'names': ['dni'],
2 |                       'groups': None,
3 |                       'dists': ['norm'],
4 |                       'bounds': [[0.6, 0.05]],
5 |                       })
6 |
7 | pvpanel = PVpanel(lat=32.117, area=1, efficiency=0.2,
8 |                  el_tilt=45, az_tilt=0)
9 | date = {'day': 144,
10 |         'hour': 14,
11 |         'minute': 0}
12 |
13 | samples = latin.sample(problem_def, sampling_size=4096)
14 |
15 | pv_power = [pvpanel.power(dni, date)[0] for dni in sample]
16 | mean = statistics.mean(pv_power)
17 | stdev = statistics.stdev(pv_power)

```

Secondly, additional parameter uncertainty is added to the calculation. As shown in Listing 3, the elevation tilt of the PV system with a mean value of 45° is uncertain with a standard derivation of 3° and the azimuth tilt with a mean value of 0° is uncertain with a standard derivation of 3°. They are added as additional factors to the problem specification and for all three 4096 samples are generated. The elevation and azimuth tilt values are used for parametrisation of the PV model and the DNI is again used for the power calculation. The result is a mean of 0.085 kW with a standard derivation of 0.0080 kW. These results are again near to the results with the analytical approach (see Section 4.5.2).

Listing 3: Sampling example with PV model and 3 factors.

```

1 | problem = ProblemSpec({'names': ['dni', 'el_tilt', 'az_tilt'],
2 |                       'groups': None,
3 |                       'dists': ['norm', 'norm', 'norm'],
4 |                       'bounds': [[0.6, 0.05], [45, 3], [0, 3]],
5 |                       })
6 |
7 | date = {'day': 144,
8 |         'hour': 14,
9 |         'minute': 0}
10 |
11 | samples = latin.sample(problem_def, sampling_size=4096)
12 |
13 | pv_panels = [PVpanel(lat=32.117, area=1, efficiency=0.2,
14 |                    el_tilt=el_tilt, az_tilt=az_tilt)
15 |              for dni, el_tilt, az_tilt in samples]
16 | pv_power = [pv_panels[count].power(values[0], date)
17 |             for count, values in enumerate(sample)]

```

⁵https://github.com/ERIGrid2/toolbox_doe_sa/blob/main/guidelines_examples/sampling_approach.py

```

16 | mean = statistics.mean(pv_power)
17 | stdev = statistics.stdev(pv_power)

```

PV System Time Series

The examples shown before were just considering one static moment in time, whereas simulation usually considers time series of data. To implement a dynamic simulation with UQ the new samples have to be generated for every simulation step as shown in Listing 4. For this simulation also a time series for the DNI is needed and also the uncertainty of the DNI is varying over the day. First, this data is read in from CSV files and prepared for usage and then a loop over the data in the CSV files is executed. The problem specification is done for each time step as it is dependent on the read-in time series data. As the date is not fixed for this simulation, it has to be set based on the CSV file. The results of the simulation are a time series as well. The mean values and the minimum and maximum error are depicted in Figure 12. The error is calculated based on the standard derivation multiplied by 3 to include more than 99% of the calculated values.

Listing 4: Sampling example with dynamic PV model.

```

1 | dni_timeseries = pd.read_csv('data\\dni_savannah_lat32_august.csv')
2 | dni_timeseries.set_index('Date', inplace=True)
3 | error_timeseries = pd.read_csv('data\\error_savannah2_August.csv')
4 | error_timeseries.set_index('Date', inplace=True)
5 | dni_data = pd.concat([dni_timeseries, error_timeseries], axis=1)
6 | results = pd.DataFrame(columns=['date', 'mean', 'stdev', 'var'])
7 | count = 0
8 | for ind, row in dni_data.iterrows():
9 |     problem = ProblemSpec({'names': ['dni'],
10 |                            'groups': None,
11 |                            'dists': ['norm'],
12 |                            'bounds': [[row['DNI'], row['Error']]],
13 |                            })
14 |     dni_samples = sample_distribution(problem, sampling_size=n)
15 |     pv_panel = PVpanel(lat=32.117, area=1, efficiency=0.2,
16 |
17 |     arrow_date = arrow.get(ind)
18 |     date = {'day': int(arrow_date.format("DDDD")),
19 |            'hour': int(arrow_date.format("hh")),
20 |            'minute': int(arrow_date.format("m"))}
21 |     pv_power = [pv_panel.power(values[0], date)
22 |                 for count, values in enumerate(dni_samples)]

```

Global Sensitivity Analysis with Sobol Indices

For further investigation of the sensitivities of parameters, one wants to know which parameters have the most effect on the outputs. A helpful method for this sensitivity analysis are Sobol indices, which compare the effects (see Section 2.3.3) (Saltelli et al., 2010).

As shown in Listing 5, one first has to define again the problem. Here, the three factors *area*, *efficiency* and *el_tilt* are defined with ranges. Based on the problem definition 4096 Sobol samples are created. For each sample, a PVPanel is created and the power is calculated with one static DNI value and used as input for the sobol indices analysis.

Figure 12: Time series sampling approach.

Listing 5: Sobol indices sensitivity analysis example.

```

1 | problem = ProblemSpec({'names': ['area', 'efficiency', 'el_tilt'],
2 |                       'groups': None,
3 |                       'dists': None,
4 |                       'bounds': [[4.0, 8.0], [0.2, 0.6], [30.0, 60.0]]
5 | })
6 | n = 4096
7 | sobol = sobol.sample(problem=problem_def, N=n,
8 |                     calc_second_order=False)
9 | date = {'day': 144,
10 |         'hour': 14,
11 |         'minute': 0}
12 | pv_panels = [PVpanel(lat=32.117, area=sample[0],
13 |                     efficiency=sample[1], el_tilt=sample[2],
14 |                     az_tilt=0)
15 |              for sample in sobol]
16 | dni = 0.6
17 | pv_power = [pvpanel.power(dni, date) for pvpanel in pv_panels]
18 | si = sbl.analyze(problem, np.asarray(pv_power),
19 |                 calc_second_order=False, conf_level=0.95,
20 |                 print_to_console=True)

```

In Figure 13, the first order index S_i and total effect index S_{T_i} are visualised (for the factors efficiency, area, and el_tilt). Additionally, the confidence is depicted as a black line, which was calculated with a confidence interval of 95%. The most important parameter in this example is efficiency, area still has some effect, while the el_tilt parameter seems to have less effect on the results. The result of this sobol indices analysis can support the user in focusing on the most relevant factors for further uncertainty analysis.

4.5.4 Uncertainty Propagation Implementation (MoReSQUE)

As introduced in Section 2.3, MoReSQUE is an UP framework for the co-simulation framework mosaik, which aims to make this quite complex approach of UQ available for co-simulation. As the approach is quite new in this context, there are still some limitations, which have to be considered. Probably the most important limitation is, that currently only stateless models can be

Figure 13: Sobol indices for PV example.

integrated. MoReSQUE can help to answer the questions regarding UQ (i.e., questions I.a and I.b) and also UP in context of system validation (i.e., question III.b) as outlined in Table 7.

Three example scenarios will be shown in this section. They have adapted evaluation examples of the MoReSQUE implementation, as described in (Steinbrink, 2017). The examples are uncertain irradiation with a PV system, the same system extended with an electricity grid. Finally, additional uncertainty in a household in the grid is added.

Table 7: Uncertainty propagation, addressing questions I.a, I.b, and III.b.

What question can this approach answer?	Question I.a, I.b, III.b
For which type of problem is this approach useful?	1a, 1c, 2b
What are the requirements to be usable?	Detailed models are available (for MoReSQUE: stateless models)
Reference to use case/example	—
Where can I find the description of foundations/tools?	UP 2.3

PV Example

In the following, the PV model example implemented with MoReSQUE is explained. Some parts of the scenario code are described in detail, but the full scenario can be found in the repository⁶. More information on how simulation scenarios are defined in mosaik is available in its documentation⁷. For that scenario, the DNI is seen as uncertain and in addition to the DNI time series an error time series is defined. The uncertain DNI is the input of the PV model, which provides the power as output.

The scenario contains a CSV simulator for reading in time series data (in this example DNI), the PV model simulator and a component for writing the results to an HDF5 file. From MoReSQUE a propagator and Output Aggregation Module (OAM) are used here. The propagator is used for the PV model and DNI data, as shown in Listing 6. It builds the ensembles and contains the configuration.

⁶https://github.com/ERIGrid2/toolbox_doe_sa/blob/main/guidelines_examples/mrsq_demo_pv.py

⁷<https://mosaik.readthedocs.io/en/latest/scenario-definition.html>

Listing 6: MoReSQUE PV example scenario.

```

1  solsim = world.start('CSV', sim_start=START, datafile=DNI_DATA)
2  so_config = {'world': world,
3              'esim_name': 'ESim', # Propagator comp. in sim_config
4              'model_name': 'Sun',
5              'sim_obj': solsim,
6              'ensemble_num': 1,
7              'u_config': U_SUN,
8              'output_config': {'Sun': ['DNI']},
9              'strat_num': 1,      # No external unc. expected
10             'step_size': 3600,
11             'start_date': START,
12             'datafile': ERROR_DATA} # Data needed for u-function
13  sol_ens = eam.EnsembleSet(so_config)
14  # Ensemble output:
15  s_outs = [s[0] for s in sol_ens.output_modules]
16  # Output aggregation module:
17  sun_oam = world.start('OAM', step_size=3600, attrs=['DNI'])
18  sun_agg = sun_oam.ItvlOut()    # Interval output is expected
19  world.connect(s_outs[0], sun_agg, 'DNI')

```

In the scenario, first, the CSV component is started (*solsim*) and added to the configuration for the propagator. Additionally, the mosaik *world*, name of the propagator and model name in the CSV component are added. The input uncertainty of DNI is provided as two separate CSV files. One contains the mean DNI data (*DNI_DATA*), while the second file contains the error of the data (*ERROR_DATA*), which is then used by the propagator module to define according to uncertainty structure (*datafile*). In the *u_config* a JSON description file is referenced (see Listing 7), which defines that the uncertainty structure is an interval and how these files are used and how the data is handled. The configuration is then used to initialise the ensemble.

Listing 7: Definition of sun uncertainty (U_SUN).

```

1  {
2      "Sun": {
3          "attrs": {
4              "DNI": {
5                  "utype": "Interval",
6                  "function": "data/sun_error.py",
7                  "kwargs": ["start_date", "datafile"]
8              }
9          },
10         "params": {}
11     }
12 }

```

The OAM is used to prepare the uncertainty structure, which is the output of CSV and PV model, for storing it to HDF5. For that, the outputs of the ensemble are selected and connected to the OAM.

The results of this scenario are depicted in Figure 14 for one simulated week. The interval for DNI values and the interval for the resulting power of the PV system can be seen.

PV Example with Grid

As a second example, some households with certain load time series and a grid model are added to the first example scenario. As the grid component gets uncertain input from the PV systems, here again, the MoReSQUE propagator is used.

Figure 14: Minimum and maximum values for Direct Normal Irradiance (DNI) and Power.

The definition is shown in Listing 8. The first lines are quite similar to the first example, but here the *input_config* is different as the input comes from another simulation component and it has to be defined where the input has to be used, so that MoReSQUE can create the according Uncertainty Quantification Modules (UQM) for the input and map it to the model. Also, some *model_params* are defined to provide the grid simulator with the topology.

Listing 8: MoReSQUE PV with load flow example scenario.

```

1 # Ensemble for power grid simulator (composite):
2 pypow = world.start('PyPower', step_size=900)
3 pow_config = {'world': world,
4               'esim_name': 'ESim',
5               'model_name': 'Grid',
6               'sim_obj': pypow,
7               'ensemble_num': 1,
8               'u_config': U_GRID,
9               'input_config': {'PQBus': {'attrs': {'P': 2},
10                                     'name': 'node'}},
11                               # Nodes receive input
12               'output_config': {'PQBus': ['Vm']},
13                               # Branches provide output
14               'strat_num': 600,
15               'step_size': 900,
16               'model_params': {'gridfile': GRID_FILE},
17               'propagation_config': {'input': {'out_grid': 600}}}
18 grid_ens = eam.EnsembleSet(pow_config)

```

In Figure 15, some of the data of this scenario simulated for 36 hours starting in the morning is visualised. The *DNI* shows an interval for the DNI, while the *House demand* is a certain time series. Based on the DNI data, the *PV generation* is calculated as a distribution and mean and quantiles are depicted. Finally, the voltage of one bus is visualised with mean and quantiles as well. One can see how the uncertainty from DNI is propagated to the voltage in the grid.

PV Example with Grid and Additional Uncertainties

The more complex uncertainty structure of p-boxes (see Section 2.2.4) is shown in an extended version of the example, which also has some additional uncertainties in household demand. The according to propagator configuration is shown in Listing 9. The *u_config* definition is

Figure 15: Uncertainty Propagation (UP) with MoReSQUE in a simulation of 36 hours.

again defined in a separate file, which is shown in Listing 10 and again points to another file, which contains the implementation. It uses a normal distribution for the uncertainty of DNI. As the uncertainty structures of the PV and household are both inputs for the grid, the output uncertainty structure is a P-Box. Thus, in Figure 16 plots for variables ending with *A* and *B* is plotted, which stand for the lower and upper distributions of the P-Box.

Listing 9: MoReSQUE PV with load flow and uncertainty in household demand example scenario.

```

1 | hhsim = world.start('CSV', sim_start=START, datafile=PROFILE_FILE)
2 | hh_config = {'world': world,
3 |             'esim_name': 'ESim',
4 |             'model_name': 'House',
5 |             'sim_obj': hhsim,
6 |             'ensemble_num': 5, # Ensembles represent five entities
7 |             'u_config': U_HH,
8 |             'output_config': {'House': ['P']},
9 |             'strat_num': 1, # No external uncertainty expected
10 |            'step_size': 900}

```

Listing 10: Definition of house uncertainty (U_HH).

```

1 | {
2 |     "House": {
3 |         "attrs": {
4 |             "P": {
5 |                 "utype": "PBox",
6 |                 "function": "data/house_error.py"

```


Figure 16: Uncertainty Propagation (UP) with MoReSQUE in a simulation of 36 hours.

4.5.5 System Validation

Validation is a crucial part of simulation or experiments to ensure that the object under investigation is sufficiently accurate for its purpose (Tsiptsias, Tako, & Robinson, 2016). Validation has usually to be done on the level of single models but can be extended to consider additionally larger systems consisting of multiple models. It is usually based on the “*comparison of model outputs with our knowledge of the real world or system.*” (Tsiptsias et al., 2016)

This can, for example, be done by comparing model outputs with experimental data. Thacker et al. provide a process description for the validation of a simulation model with an experiment, which is shown in Figure 17 (Thacker et al., 2004). It shows the development of a conceptual model to abstract the real world as the first step. This conceptual model is then implemented in a validation experiment and a mathematical model, which is again implemented as a computer model. The outcomes of the experiment and simulation are in the end compared to validate the simulation model against the real-world experiment data. For that, uncertainty quantification of both models is an additional important step. In the end, it has to be decided if the model is “good enough”.

In the following, aspects of this process are described in more detail based on the description of (Thacker et al., 2004).

It has to be mentioned, that in the HTD the characteristics of a validation test are described as “*functional requirements and abstract measures are provided, but are subject to interpretation; qualitative test criteria. Example: is a controller ready for deployment?*” (ERIGrid/Holistic-Test-Description: v0.5, 2019). In this description, the comparison aspect is not present as it is meant in this section and should not be confused. System validation focuses on answering questions III.a and III.b regarding the representational uncertainty (cf. Table 8 and Figure 17).

Table 8: System validation, addressing questions III.a, III.b.

What question can this approach answer?	Questions III.a, III.b
For which type of problem is this approach useful?	1a, 1c, 1b, 2a, 2b
What are the requirements to be usable?	(automatically) repeatable simulation/lab setup
Reference to use case / example	–
Where can I find the description of foundations / tools?	the section below

Figure 17: Validation and Uncertainty Quantification (Thacker et al., 2004, p.7).

Validation Assessment

As described in (Thacker et al., 2004) “Validation assessment is the process of determining the degree to which a model is an accurate representation of the real world from the perspective of the intended uses of the model.” It is based on the comparison of the output of the model or model prediction with experimental data. The formulation “process of determining” implies that it is an ongoing activity. All results from the model and experiment will contain uncertainty as indicated by “degree of which”. This is usually formulated as a statistical statement for agreement, for example, expected error + confidence limits. The validation assessment is only for a specific use case (“intended use of the model”) and new use cases would need new validation assessment.

Validation Hierarchy

Usually, the considered systems can be quite complex and consist of subsystems and components, which might have unknown dependencies. The validation of the whole system in one step is problematic, as problems on lower levels could be cancelled due to coupling effects. Thus, validation should be done step by step starting from the lowest level. If there are not enough resources for this approach, sensitivity analysis on the system level can help to show which parts of the system are most relevant and should have the focus. Another approach could be an expert judgement of uncertainties and propagation of these uncertainties to the top level.

Validation Metrics

Because simulation can produce an immense amount of data, the most relevant results have to be chosen. This selection should be based on the validation requirement phase of the conceptual model development. For the comparison of model and experiment results, validation metrics have to be defined. These base on the error e , experimental data y , and model results y^* , which can be described as:

$$y^* : e = y - y^*$$

Metrics can be simply the value of the error $E(e)$ or variance of the error $V(e)$, $P(e > 0)$ with $P(\cdot)$ as probability, 95th percentile of the probability distribution of e , or a hypothesis test. Further information about validation metrics can also be found in (Trucano et al., 2001; Trucano, Pilch, & Oberkampf, 2002).

Validation Experiments

The documentation and control of all parameters (e.g., specimen geometry, initial conditions, boundary conditions, and other model input parameters) are crucial for validation experiments and other experiment results usually do not fulfil these requirements. To be able to use the experiment output for validation of the model, the accuracy and precision of experimental data have to be estimated. Thus, the uncertainty of the measurement has to be estimated. For experiments, errors can be categorised as random error (precision) and systematic error (bias). Random error leads to scatter in the data in repeated experiments and can be seen as aleatory uncertainty. They produce non-deterministic effects and can not be reduced with additional testing. Systematic error can be seen as epistemic uncertainty, is reproducible and can be theoretically reduced, but that might be difficult.

To consider measurement uncertainties, the accuracy and precision of measurements have to be known. For this, calibration and documentation of inaccuracies is crucial. The estimation and characterisation of the uncertainties can be done (1) based on the elemental uncertainties, which lead together to the total experimental error or (2) based on replicated testing to get a direct statistical estimate of total uncertainty. Both approaches can also be combined.

Uncertainty Quantification

Simulation and experiment results will always contain uncertainty, which has to be quantified to not falsify validation. As described in Section 2.1.1 uncertainty can be categorised as aleatory (irreducible) and epistemic (reducible). For irreducible (aleatory) uncertainty sampling approaches with repeated experiments can be used to estimate uncertainty (see Section 4.5.3). If that is not possible, expert opinion can be used, but these might add additional uncertainty.)

Validation Requirements and Acceptable Agreement

The last step of system validation is to assess the accuracy of the model by comparing the results of the model and the experiment based on the requirement defined at the beginning of the process.

5 Use Cases

Based on the previous guidelines section, which showed the different approaches with an educational basic example, in this section some more complex and relevant use cases are shown. The use cases are chosen from the research work in ERIGrid 2.0 project. The implementation is provided if possible, but as some use cases are still under development not all implementations can be references here as open source material.

Section 5.1 is based on the Multi-Energy Benchmark scenario developed (Widl, Wild, Heussen, Rikos, & Hoang, 2022; *ERIGrid2/benchmark-model-multi-energy-networks: v1.0*, n.d.). It shows how sensitivity analysis and uncertainty quantification can be applied to the Multi-Energy Benchmark scenario. Section 5.2 is based on multi-energy district flexibility, which might use the toolbox and also other approaches later when the implementation is finished. Section 5.3 illustrates time delay compensation as example to apply the analytical approach.

5.1 Multi-Energy Benchmark

5.1.1 Overview

In earlier stages of ERIGrid 2.0, a set of simulation benchmark models were developed including different energy domains and system representations. The aforementioned benchmarks are: (i) Electrical Network, (ii) Multi-energy Networks, and (iii) ICT-enhanced Power System. These benchmarks aimed to provide a reference framework for the validation of smart grid concepts and technologies to be studied in further activities of ERIGrid 2.0 project and, at the same time, serve as examples for further researches (D'Arco et al., 2022; *ERIGrid2/benchmark-model-multi-energy-networks: v1.0*, n.d.; Widl et al., 2022).

In this case, the functionalities of the toolbox for SA and UQ are tested by using the multi-energy networks benchmark. In order to understand how the toolbox functionality is applied, it is crucial to understand how this benchmark is structured.

The multi-energy networks benchmark is a representation of a multi-carrier energy system in which a thermal and electrical distribution network are connected through a power-to-heat facility and linked by a control system as shown in Figure 18. This model was designed to focus on energy management and control scheme for multi-energy systems and allows to understand the complexity on dealing with in a multi-domain co-simulation environment.

Figure 18: Overview of the overall system configuration used in the multi-energy benchmark model.

In the electrical domain, the model is composed of two buses connected to an external grid, each one with a PV generation and load (which simulates the consumer) associated. One of these buses also includes a voltage control system which regulates the heat pump and tank. On the other side, in the thermal domain, the group heat pump and storage tank are connected to an external district heat system and, at the same time, are regulated through a voltage control system.

5.1.2 Scenario Example

To illustrate how the toolbox for sensitivity analysis works, the multi-energy benchmark model has been selected to be processed. The target metrics in these cases include the grid voltages (maximum and minimum values estimated), line losses, loading percentage, and thermal supply temperature (maximum and minimum values), among others. Moreover, the parameters that are varied are the storage tank's inner diameter, PV generation and transmission line length. The detailed input file which details the values set for each parameter of the model can be found at the related GitHub repository⁸.

In order to illustrate how the simulation results are generated, Figure 19 shows the simulation results plotting the relation between three of the variable analysed: storage tank's inner diameter, PV generation scale (respect to the base time-series value) and self-consumption. From the results, for instance, it can be concluded that as the PV generation scale increases, the self-consumption increases consequently. This can be explained by the fact that as the scale is higher the more PV electricity is generated which leads to an increase in the energy available to be consumed in the bus bars and therefore, less energy is exchanged with the external electrical grid. In other words, the self-consumption (autonomy) increases with the increase in PV generation. In contrast, the storage tank's inner diameter and self-consumption are variables which have no strong correlation since variation in the tank dimensions produces not have a consistent effect on the self-consumption.

Figure 19: Illustration of simulation results for multi-energy benchmark case study considering three variables: storage tank's inner diameter, PV generation, self-consumption.

⁸https://github.com/ERIGrid2/toolbox_doe_sa

5.2 Multi-Energy District Flexibility

5.2.1 Overview

This use case aims similarly like the multi-energy benchmark to examine the technical feasibility of utilising power-to-heat in a local multi-energy district, and to assess its impact on both the electric and thermal networks. By combining electric and thermal storage systems and incorporating flexible loads, such as heat pumps, thermal loads, and electric boilers, This use case will explore the ability of the heating system to offer services to the electrical system, including congestion management and balancing power provision.

Figure 20 provides an overview of the SuT. It includes a district heating system, an electrical system and a control system. The thermal system is composed of two subsystems, one connected to a district heating network and interfaced to the electrical system through a Combined Heat and Power (CHP) unit and another one fed by a heat pump.

The electrical system is composed of three main physical feeders and a simulated grid portion. The physical feeders connect a simulated battery Energy Storage System (ESS), a CHP and a heat pump. The control system determines the set-points for the controllable resources in order to provide the requested services, which concern mainly the control of the power at the electrical network Point of Common Coupling (PCC).

Figure 20: Schematic representation of the use case multi-energy district flexibility

The purpose of the test is the verification the impact of local flexibility on available regulating power from a local district. The performance will be assessed through the power exchanges at the electrical network PCC, following requests from the Distribution System Operator (DSO) and the appropriate control of the various means of flexibility offered by the multi-energy district.

As multi-energy districts are complex systems that are difficult to replicate in a laboratory setting, this test case demonstrates the possibility to perform tests by integrating resources from different RIs, creating an extended RI with greater capabilities than any single laboratory. The multi-energy district will be emulated by integrating equipment across multiple RIs, by utilising tools developed in ERIGrid 2.0 project for data exchange and interconnection among RIs.

5.2.2 Usage of Practical Guidelines

Multiple aspects of the guidelines at hand can support the handling of uncertainties in multi-energy district flexibility.

Using the extended HTD template can help in uncertainty assessment, which consists of the identification of uncertainty sources and classifying them. With the help of the HTD template (see Section 3.1) this can be supported. The classification can help to answer Question II.b (*“How can the uncertainty be further reduced (if possible)?”*) by identifying the type of uncertainties and focusing on the uncertainties, which can be reduced.

In the HTD description of DEMO4 there are already some controllable factors (heat pumps set-point, electrical and thermal storage system set-point), and uncontrollable factors (electrical and thermal demand and PV generation) listed. Also, the two target metrics electrical energy bound violation [MWh] and electrical energy balance deviation [MWh] are defined. The energy metrics concern integration of the deviations of power from target values, over the period of the experiment. This information can be directly used for the extended HTD template and further categorised.

By using the toolbox, the reproducibility of the experiment, in terms of the controllable factors, can be supported, as the configuration and parameterisation of the experiment are defined in the proposed data structure. Thus, the configuration of all components is made available in one JSON file to support the implementation of the experiment. The same data structure can also be used for directly applying sampling strategies and analysis methods and providing configuration files with recipes for automated execution of multiple simulation runs and UQ of the results or SA. Thus, it can help to answer questions 1a and 1b (UQ) and 2a (SA). It is noted, that as the testing involves parts with physical experiments and uncontrollable factors have already been identified, several repetitions will probably be required in order to cover a wide range of conditions and conclude on the test’s Pol.

5.3 Example of Analytical Approach for Time Delay Compensation

5.3.1 A Recap of Time Delay Compensation Use Case

To support the pace of transition required by climate policy commitments, the complexity of power systems is increasing with the emergence of active power network controls, high penetrations of converter-interfaced distributed generation, new digitisation schemes, etc. Correspondingly, there is a growing need to find novel techniques for real-time simulation and Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL) experimentation that can characterise the interactions between novel control schemes and emerging power technologies under a vastly greater range of operating conditions.

Consequently, the concept of Geographically Distributed Real-Time Simulation (GDRTS), as depicted in Figure 21, was proposed and explored to support the adoption of novel real-time simulation and HIL techniques for the whole energy system simulation across the geographically distributed RIs (M. H. Syed et al., 2021). In analogy to the conventional Power Hardware-in-the-Loop (PHIL) setup, the inherent time delay within the GDRTS closed-loop setup is variable yet deterministic and plays a detrimental role in the stability and accuracy of the GDRTS setup, where two or more Digital Real-Time Simulation (DRTS) are interconnected over the internet through a dedicated interface as leveraged in PHIL setups (Feng, Peña-Alzola, Syed, Norman, & Burt, 2023). The indeterministic nature of the power signal data exchange through

Figure 21: Representation of simulation setups.

the internet not only results in a remarkably large time delay in the GDRTS closed-loop setup but also presents a remarkable challenge for the characterisation of the time delay and its consequential quantification and compensation, which are crucial for realising robust GDRTS with high-fidelity (M. H. Syed et al., 2021; M. Syed et al., 2022).

The test demonstration for time delay compensation encompasses the development of time delay quantification and compensation methods to support the adoption of GDRTS setups for smart grid applications. The time delay arising from multiple stages, such as digital processing of simulation platforms, signal conversion, and communication latency, is a key factor in determining the stability and accuracy of the GDRTS. Therefore, it is essential to conduct a comprehensive characterisation and in-depth analysis of the time delay before deploying a GDRTS system in its final stage. Furthermore, advanced time delay compensation methodologies are essential for ensuring the robustness and fidelity of GDRTS, with precise power synchronisation and transparent power transfer across the candidate RIs.

From an application perspective, the time delay with time-varying, non-uniform, and irregular attributes can be regarded as an uncertainty factor that affects the stability and accuracy of robust GDRTS operation. This section investigates the time delay through an analytical approach to UQ in a probabilistic manner. Additionally, it illustrates the propagation of uncertainty in the time delay on the closed-loop setup of GDRTS.

5.3.2 GDRTS System Modelling

As shown in Figure 21, GDRTS setup combines two geographically distributed laboratories with real-time emulated systems into a closed-loop testing configuration that mimics the original System of Interest (SoI) in one single simulation configuration. Correspondingly, Figure 22 illustrates the equivalent diagram of the GDRTS setup comprising two interconnected subsystem 1 (S_1) and subsystem 2 (S_2), which are expressed in the form of a lumped voltage divider topology with two series-connected Thévenin equivalent circuits. Subsystem $S_1(s)$ consists of an equivalent voltage source V_S in series with an equivalent impedance $Z_1 (R_1 + sL_1)$ of the subsystem 1 and system S_2 comprises one equivalent impedance $Z_2 (R_2 + sL_2)$. As illustrated in Figure 22, a signal conversion, signal processing, and data communication-based interface bridges these two subsystems, thereby closing the simulation loop.

The coupling of subsystems S_1 and S_2 that are split from SoI and geographically distributed across different RIs is subjected to the interface algorithms being adopted. Among the interface algorithms presented in (Lauss et al., 2016), Ideal Transformer Model (ITM) interface is the most extensively utilised as a result of its ease of implementation and relatively high and acceptable stability and accuracy performance. In this case study, the voltage-type ITM interface

Figure 22: Representation of the equivalent model of the simulation setup.

is employed to define the power transmission and synchronisation manner within the GDRTS setup. As shown in Figure 22, the voltage-type ITM interface is configured as a controllable voltage source in subsystem S_2 that amplifies the voltage signal measure at the coupling point in subsystems S_1 , while the current response from subsystems S_2 is fed back to subsystems S_1 by means of a controlled current source. By doing so, the dynamics in both subsystems are replicated to each other and the simulation loop is interconnected.

From the system modelling point of view, the GDRTS system is represented in the form of a Single-Input-Single-Output (SISO) closed-loop system and the respective equivalent block diagram with all key components and interface signals are presented in Figure 23. The open-loop transfer function of this GDRTS closed-loop system is represented as,

$$T_O(s) = \underbrace{T_{FF1}(s)T_{FF2}(s)e^{-s\tau_{ff}}}_{T_{FF}(s)} \underbrace{T_{FB1}(s)T_{FB2}(s)e^{-s\tau_{fb}}}_{T_{FB}(s)} \frac{Z_1(s)}{Z_2(s)}, \quad (5)$$

where $Z_1(s)$ and $Z_2(s)$ are the equivalent impedance of the subsystem S_1 and subsystem S_2 , respectively. $T_{FF}(s)$ is the transfer function of the interface in the feed-forward path comprising the transfer functions of signal conversion and processing units $T_{FF1}(s)$, data communication unit $T_{FF2}(s)$, and the aggregated time delay τ_{ff} in the feed-forward path. $T_{FB}(s)$ represents the transfer function of the interface in the feedback path consisting of the transfer functions of signal conversion and processing units $T_{FB1}(s)$, data communication unit $T_{FB2}(s)$, and the aggregated time delay τ_{fb} in the feedback path. The aggregated time delay in GDRTS closed-loop is given by,

$$\tau = \tau_{ff} + \tau_{fb} \quad (6)$$

The open-loop transfer function eq. (5) is further expressed as,

$$T_O(s) = \underbrace{T_{FF1}(s)T_{FF2}(s)T_{FF3}(s)T_{FF4}(s)}_{T_O^*(s)} e^{-s\tau} \frac{Z_1(s)}{Z_2(s)}, \quad (7)$$

where $T_O^*(s)$ is the delay-free part of the GDRTS interface.

Figure 23: Equivalent block diagram of the simulation setup in a SISO representation manner.

5.3.3 Uncertainty Representation of the Time Delay within GDRTS Setup

Developing a comprehensive understanding of time delay and its effects is crucial in minimising the risk of instabilities and inaccuracies during GDRTS experiments, allowing more robust and accurate evaluation of complex power systems and power apparatus. Thoroughly characterising delays in GDRTS may also help reduce the total loop delay and improve its accuracy. Therefore, identifying the characteristics of the delay, particularly its variability and uncertainty, is the first step towards a better understanding of it. To collect the experimental time delay data, Raspberry Pi devices were deployed across the DPSL and PNDC at the University of Strathclyde, Glasgow, United Kingdom. The two locations are geographically separated by a distance of 23.5 km (14.6 miles).

To demonstrate the variability of the time delay within the GDRTS setup, the aggregated total loop time delay data between these geographically distributed DPSL and PNDC labs over a randomly selected period was presented in Figure 24.

Figure 24: Simulation time delay between DPSL and PNDC over a selected period.

It is evident that the loop time delay is time-varying and presents non-uniform, and irregular characteristics. The variability of the time delay in GDRTS may be attributed to various factors, including signal conversion, coding and decoding of the interfacing signals, digital data communication, and the loss of UDP packets. These factors are intrinsic properties of the system and can contribute to the overall variability of the time delay. Consequently, the time delay is a critical uncertainty factor that must be carefully considered during the design of the GDRTS

experimental setup. Having a comprehensive uncertainty representation and quantification of the time delay variability is of great significance for the GDRTS design and operation.

In an effort to quantify the uncertainty of the time delay within the GDRTS setup, the statistical techniques as elaborated in Section 2.2 are employed to process the time delay data presented in Figure 24. At the initial stage, the time delay data is grouped into 100 bins that are evenly distributed across the range of time delays collected within the GDRTS setup. The relative probability ρ_i of each time delay bin i can be calculated as

$$\rho_i = \frac{c_i}{N}, \quad (8)$$

where c_i is the cumulative number of observations for each time delay bin, and N is the total number of time delay samples. The frequency of observations for each time delay bin is represented in the histogram shown in Figure 25, which provides insights into the underlying numerical distribution of time delays. Furthermore, the histogram shown in Figure 25 is normalised by dividing the cumulative number of observations for each time delay bin by the total number of time delay samples as in eq. (8). This normalisation allows us to illustrate the relative probability of a time delay value falling within each time delay bin, as illustrated in Figure 26.

Figure 25: Histogram of simulation time delay distribution between DPSL and PNDC.

Figure 26: Histogram of simulation time delay normalised distribution between DPSL and PNDC and its relative probability.

The relative probability of the variable delay falling within the bin edges [12.75 ms, 12.86 ms] is the highest, reaching a value of 9.8%. On the other hand, the relative probability of the variable delay falling within the bin edges at the lowest and greatest values of the range, i.e., [12.40 ms, 12.52 ms] and [23.88 ms, 24.0 ms], respectively, is the lowest, measuring at 0.11%. This

further reveals the time-varying and non-uniform characteristics of the GDRTS time delay in a probabilistic manner, which contributes towards the assessment of the impact of the time delay variability and its associated uncertainty on the GDRTS stability and accuracy.

To substantially unify the probability distribution characteristics of the time delay variability and quantify its associated uncertainty, the following probability density function estimation was employed:

$$PDF = \frac{\rho_i}{w_i}, \quad (9)$$

where ρ_i is the relative probability as in eq. (8), and w_i is the width of the time delay bin.

Note that the time delay within the GDRTS setup is considered as an aleatory uncertainty resulting from intrinsic fluctuations of the system and presents continuous random values, ranging from 12.40 ms and 24.0 ms. Figure 27 depicts the PDF estimation curve, which enables the calculation of the probability of the variable time delay falling within a specific range of delay values by summing up the area covered by the PDF estimation curve. The sum of the area covered by the PDF estimation curve is 1. As shown in Figure 27, the steep areas of the PDF estimation curve over the time delay bin [12.75 ms, 12.86 ms] indicate the most probable time delay values.

Figure 27: Normalised probability density function of simulation time delay distribution between DPSL and PNDC.

The uncertainty is represented as a distribution of probability distributions, which indicates the relative likelihood that the value of the bounded random variable would fall within a specific range. This representation allows for a better understanding of the probability distribution of the variable GDRTS time delay and its associated uncertainty.

5.3.4 Uncertainty Propagation of the Time Delay within GDRTS Setup

One can translate the feedback loop from Figure 23 into the equation

$$l_2 = \frac{1}{Z_2} T_{FF} (V_1 - Z_1 T_{FB} l_2),$$

where every variable is actually a function of the complex frequency s (which we suppress in the notation for simplicity). T_{FF} and T_{FB} are as in eq. (5), i.e.

$$\begin{aligned} T_{FF}(s) &= T_{FF1}(s) T_{FF2}(s) e^{-sT_{ff}}, \\ T_{FB}(s) &= T_{FB1}(s) T_{FB2}(s) e^{-sT_{fb}}. \end{aligned}$$

Extracting l_2 , we get

$$l_2 = (T_{FF}^{-1}Z_2 + Z_1 T_{FB})^{-1} V_1.$$

For any fixed frequency s , we want to consider the uncertainty of l_2 given the uncertainties in the input V_1 , and the time delays τ_{ff} , and τ_{fb} . As $\frac{\partial T_{FF}}{\partial \tau_{ff}} = -sT_{FF}$ (and similar for T_{FB}), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial l_2}{\partial V_1} &= (T_{FF}^{-1}Z_2 + Z_1 T_{FB})^{-1}, \\ \frac{\partial l_2}{\partial \tau_{ff}} &= (T_{FF}^{-1}Z_2 + Z_1 T_{FB})^{-2} Z_2 T_{FF}^{-1} s V_1, \\ \frac{\partial l_2}{\partial \tau_{fb}} &= -(T_{FF}^{-1}Z_2 + Z_1 T_{FB})^{-2} Z_1 T_{FB} s V_1, \end{aligned}$$

which combine to give

$$\sigma_{l_2} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial l_2}{\partial V_1}\right)^2 \sigma_{V_1}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial l_2}{\partial \tau_{ff}}\right)^2 \sigma_{\tau_{ff}}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial l_2}{\partial \tau_{fb}}\right)^2 \sigma_{\tau_{fb}}^2}.$$

Of course, this analysis is only a simplification, as in the real experiment, the delays τ_{ff} and τ_{fb} will vary during the experiment, instead of being just uncertain.

6 Conclusions

The goal of this deliverable is to aid researchers in the energy domain to deal with uncertainty in their results in a systematic and reproducible fashion. To this end, the established HTD from the ERIGrid project was extended in this research work to include explicit uncertainty considerations on all three levels (Test Case, Test Specification and Experiment Specification). In particular, researchers must identify the type of uncertainty with which they are dealing, so we elaborate on different types and flavours of uncertainty.

Depending on the identified types of uncertainty and other details of the problem, different ways of quantifying and propagating the uncertainty are feasible and appropriate. We provide an overview of a subset of the existing techniques. We also provide a series of typical research questions concerning uncertainty, to aid researchers in selecting the right technique for their case. We then apply these techniques ourselves to an educational example and some prototypical examples from other work packages and tasks of the ERIGrid 2.0 project.

While developing novel techniques for dealing with uncertainty was out of the scope of this document, research into further new methods for dealing with uncertainty seems a worthwhile endeavour. In particular, possibility theory appears to be a promising way of dealing with epistemic uncertainty that is more fine-grained than simple intervals. Here, the propagation of the possibility distribution through models still seems to be an open question, in particular when combined with probabilistic distributions and when using sampling approaches.

For more efficient propagation of uncertainties through complex co-simulation setups, we found MoReSQUE to be a promising start. However, its black-box view on simulators makes it difficult to deal with stateful simulations, as they would lead to combinatorial explosions quickly, and MoReSQUE therefore restricts to stateless models. The ERIGrid 2.0 consortium feels that an approach that incorporates uncertainty into the simulators as well (instead of just the co-simulation framework), might enable dealing with a wider range of simulations. This would be a significant research and development task.

References

- Aien, M., Rashidinejad, M., & Fotuhi-Firuzabad, M. (2014). On possibilistic and probabilistic uncertainty assessment of power flow problem: A review and a new approach. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*(37), 883–895.
- Bain, L., & Engelhardt, M. (1992). *Introduction to probability and mathematical statistics*. Brooks/Cole Cengage Learning. Retrieved from <https://books.google.de/books?id=MkFRIAAACAAJ>
- Baraldi, P., Popescu, I. C., & Zio, E. (2010). Methods of uncertainty analysis in prognostics. *International Journal of Performance Engineering*, 6(4), 303–330.
- Deardorff, D. (2000). *Measurement and Uncertainty Analysis* (Tech. Rep.). University of North Carolina, Department of Physics and Astronomy. Retrieved from <https://users.physics.unc.edu/~deardorff/uncertainty/UNCguide.pdf>
- de Cooman, G., & Walley, P. (2002). A possibilistic hierarchical model for behaviour under uncertainty. *Theory and Decision*, 52(4), 327–374. doi:10.1023/a:1020296514974
- Dubois, D., & Prade, H. (2001). Possibility theory, probability theory and multiple-valued logics: A clarification. *Annals of Mathematics and Artificial Intelligence*, 32, 35–66. doi:10.1023/A:1016740830286
- D’Arco, S., Paola, A. D., Widl, E., Rajkumar, V. S., Kamsamrong, J., Raussi, P., ... Cortés-Borray, A. F. (2022). *D-JRA1.1 Benchmark Scenarios* (Tech. Rep.). doi:10.5281/zenodo.4032691
- ERIGrid2/benchmark-model-multi-energy-networks: v1.0*. (n.d.). The ERIGrid 2.0 Consortium. doi:10.5281/zenodo.5735005
- ERIGrid/Holistic-Test-Description: v0.5*. (2019). The ERIGrid Consortium. doi:10.5281/zenodo.3256157
- ERIGrid/NA4-SummerSchool-DTU-2018: v2.0*. (n.d.). The ERIGrid Consortium. doi:10.5281/zenodo.2837928
- Feitelson, D. G. (2015, January). From repeatability to reproducibility and corroboration. In *Operating systems review (acm)* (Vol. 49, pp. 3–11). doi:10.1145/2723872.2723875
- Feng, Z., Peña-Alzola, R., Syed, M. H., Norman, P. J., & Burt, G. M. (2023). Adaptive smith predictor for enhanced stability of power hardware-in-the-loop setups. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, 70(10), 10204–10214. doi:10.1109/TIE.2022.3224196
- Ferson, S., Kreinovich, V., Ginzburg, L., Myers, D. S., & Sentz, K. (2003). *Constructing Probability Boxes and Dempster-Shafer Structures* (Tech. Rep. No. January). Albuquerque, New Mexico: Sandia National Laboratories.
- Gaber, N., Foley, G., Pascual, P., Stiber, N., & Sunderland, E. (2009). *Guidance on the development, evaluation, and application of environmental models* (Tech. Rep.). Washington, DC 20460: U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA).
- Geman, S., & Geman, D. (1984). Stochastic relaxation, gibbs distributions, and the bayesian restoration of images. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, PAMI-6(6), 721–741. doi:10.1109/TPAMI.1984.4767596

- Geyer, C. (2011). *Handbook of markov chain monte carlo*. New York: Chapman and Hall/CRC. doi:[10.1201/b10905-2](https://doi.org/10.1201/b10905-2)
- Giunta, A. A., Wojtkiewicz, S. F., & Eldred, M. S. (2003). Overview of modern design of experiments methods for computational simulations. In *41st aerospace sciences meeting and exhibit*. doi:[10.2514/6.2003-649](https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2003-649)
- Gralla, E., & Szajnarfarber, Z. (2016). Characterizing Representational Uncertainty in System Design and Operations. *Systems Engineering*, 19(6), 535–548. doi:[10.1002/sys.21375](https://doi.org/10.1002/sys.21375)
- Herman, J., & Usher, W. (2017, January). SALib: An open-source python library for sensitivity analysis. *The Journal of Open Source Software*, 2(9). doi:[10.21105/joss.00097](https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.00097)
- Heussen, K., Steinbrink, C., Abdulhadi, I. F., Nguyen, V. H., Degefa, M. Z., Merino, J., . . . Strasser, T. I. (2019). Erigrad holistic test description for validating cyber-physical energy systems. *Energies*, 12, 1–31. doi:[10.3390/en12142722](https://doi.org/10.3390/en12142722)
- IEC Glossary Entry. (2009). *Intrinsic uncertainty of the measurand*. <https://std.iec.ch/terms/terms.nsf/9bc7f244dab1a789c12570590045fac8/7acae9665251c1c1c1257562004eb819?OpenDocument>. (Accessed: 2023-05-31)
- Iwanaga, T., Usher, W., & Herman, J. (2022, May). Toward SALib 2.0: Advancing the accessibility and interpretability of global sensitivity analyses. *Socio-Environmental Systems Modelling*, 4, 18155. doi:[10.18174/sesmo.18155](https://doi.org/10.18174/sesmo.18155)
- Janssen, H. (2013). Monte-Carlo based uncertainty analysis: Sampling efficiency and sampling convergence. *Reliability Engineering and System Safety*, 109(November), 123–132. doi:[10.1016/j.res.2012.08.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.res.2012.08.003)
- Jones, M. C., Marron, J. S., & Sheather, S. J. (1996). A brief survey of bandwidth selection for density estimation. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 91(433), 401–407. doi:[10.1080/01621459.1996.10476701](https://doi.org/10.1080/01621459.1996.10476701)
- Kennedy, M. C., & O'Hagan, A. (2001). Bayesian calibration of computer models. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society: Series B (Statistical Methodology)*, 63(3), 425–464.
- Kiureghian, A. D., & Ditlevsen, O. (2009). Aleatory or epistemic? does it matter? *Structural Safety*, 31(2), 105–112. doi:[10.1016/j.strusafe.2008.06.020](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.strusafe.2008.06.020)
- Kleijnen, J. P. (2015). *Design and Analysis of Simulation Experiments (International Series in Operations Research & Management Science)*. doi:[10.1007/978-3-319-18087-8](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-18087-8)
- Lauss, G. F., Faruque, M. O., Schoder, K., Dufour, C., Viehweider, A., & Langston, J. (2016, January). Characteristics and design of power hardware-in-the-loop simulations for electrical power systems. *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, 63(1), 406–417. doi:[10.1109/TIE.2015.2464308](https://doi.org/10.1109/TIE.2015.2464308)
- McKay, M. D., Beckman, R. J., & Conover, W. J. (1979). A comparison of three methods for selecting values of input variables in the analysis of output from a computer code. *Technometrics*, 21(2), 239–245. doi:[10.2307/1268522](https://doi.org/10.2307/1268522)
- Metropolis, N., Rosenbluth, A. W., Rosenbluth, M. N., Teller, A. H., & Teller, E. (2004, December). Equation of State Calculations by Fast Computing Machines. *The Journal of Chemical Physics*, 21(6), 1087–1092. doi:[10.1063/1.1699114](https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1699114)
- Mulenga, E., Bollen, M. H., & Etherden, N. (2021). Solar pv stochastic hosting capacity in distribution networks considering aleatory and epistemic uncertainties. *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, 130, 106928. doi:[10.1016/j.ijepes.2021.106928](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijepes.2021.106928)

- Parzen, E. (1962). On Estimation of a Probability Density Function and Mode. *The Annals of Mathematical Statistics*, 33(3), 1065–1076. doi:[10.1214/aoms/1177704472](https://doi.org/10.1214/aoms/1177704472)
- Pianosi, F., Beven, K., Freer, J., Hall, J. W., Rougier, J., Stephenson, D. B., & Wagener, T. (2016). Sensitivity analysis of environmental models: A systematic review with practical workflow. *Environmental Modelling & Software*, 79, 214–232. doi:[10.1016/j.envsoft.2016.02.008](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2016.02.008)
- Rosenblatt, M. (1956). Remarks on Some Nonparametric Estimates of a Density Function. *The Annals of Mathematical Statistics*, 27(3), 832–837. doi:[10.1214/aoms/1177728190](https://doi.org/10.1214/aoms/1177728190)
- Saltelli, A. (2002). Making best use of model evaluations to compute sensitivity indices. *Computer Physics Communications*, 145(2), 280–297. doi:[10.1016/S0010-4655\(02\)00280-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0010-4655(02)00280-1)
- Saltelli, A., Annoni, P., Azzini, I., Campolongo, F., Ratto, M., & Tarantola, S. (2010, February). Variance based sensitivity analysis of model output. Design and estimator for the total sensitivity index. *Computer Physics Communications*, 181(2), 259–270. doi:[10.1016/j.cpc.2009.09.018](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpc.2009.09.018)
- Saltelli, A., Tarantola, S., & Chan, K. P.-S. (1999). A quantitative model-independent method for global sensitivity analysis of model output. *Technometrics*, 41(1), 39–56. doi:[10.1080/00401706.1999.10485594](https://doi.org/10.1080/00401706.1999.10485594)
- Shafer, G. (1976). *A mathematical theory of evidence*. Princeton: Princeton University Press. doi:[10.1515/9780691214696](https://doi.org/10.1515/9780691214696)
- Sobol', I. (1967). On the distribution of points in a cube and the approximate evaluation of integrals. *USSR Computational Mathematics and Mathematical Physics*, 7(4), 86–112. doi:[10.1016/0041-5553\(67\)90144-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0041-5553(67)90144-9)
- Sobol, I. M. (2001). Global sensitivity indices for nonlinear mathematical models and their Monte Carlo estimates. *Mathematics and Computers in Simulation*, 55(1-3), 271–280. doi:[10.1016/S0378-4754\(00\)00270-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-4754(00)00270-6)
- Steinbrink, C. (2017). *A Non-Intrusive Uncertainty Quantification System for Modular Smart Grid Co-Simulation* (PhD). University of Oldenburg.
- Syed, M., Hoang, T. T., Kontou, A., Paspatis, A., Burt, G., Tran, Q. T., ... Hatzigargyriou, N. (2022). Applicability of geographically distributed simulations. *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, 1–15. doi:[10.1109/TPWRS.2022.3197635](https://doi.org/10.1109/TPWRS.2022.3197635)
- Syed, M. H., Guillo-Sansano, E., Wang, Y., Vogel, S., Palensky, P., Burt, G. M., ... Hovsapian, R. (2021). Real-time coupling of geographically distributed research infrastructures: Taxonomy, overview, and real-world smart grid applications. *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, 12(2), 1747–1760. doi:[10.1109/TSG.2020.3033070](https://doi.org/10.1109/TSG.2020.3033070)
- Thacker, B. H., Doebling, S. W., Hemez, F. M., Anderson, M. C., Pepin, J. E., & Rodriguez, E. a. (2004). Concepts of Model Verification and Validation. *Concepts of Model Verification and Validation*, 41.
- Thunnissen, D. P. (2003). Uncertainty Classification for the Design and Development of Complex Systems. *3rd Annual Predictive Methods Conference*, 16. Retrieved from <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.128.133&rep=rep1&type=pdf>
- Trucano, T. G., Easterling, R. G., Dowding, K. J., Paez, T. L., Urbina, A., Romero, V. J., ... Hills, R. G. (2001). *Description of the Sandia Validation Metrics Project* (Tech. Rep. No.

August). Albuquerque, New Mexico and Livermore, California: Sandia National Laboratories. Retrieved from <https://www.osti.gov/servlets/purl/786623>

Trucano, T. G., Pilch, M., & Oberkampf, W. L. (2002). *General Concepts for Experimental Validation of ASCI Code Applications* (Tech. Rep. No. March). Albuquerque, New Mexico and Livermore, California: Sandia National Laboratories. Retrieved from <https://www.osti.gov/servlets/purl/800777>

Tsiptsias, N., Tako, A., & Robinson, S. (2016). Model validation and testing in simulation: A literature review. *OpenAccess Series in Informatics*, 50(6), 6.1–6.11. doi:[10.4230/OASICS.SCOR.2016.6](https://doi.org/10.4230/OASICS.SCOR.2016.6)

Van Der Meer, A. A., Steinbrink, C., Heussen, K., Bondy, D. E., Degefa, M. Z., Andrn, F. P., ... Palensky, P. (2018). Design of experiments aided holistic testing of cyber-physical energy systems. *2018 Workshop on Modeling and Simulation of Cyber-Physical Energy Systems, MSCPES 2018 - Held as part of CPS Week, Proceedings*, 1–7. doi:[10.1109/MSCPES.2018.8405401](https://doi.org/10.1109/MSCPES.2018.8405401)

van der Meer, A. A., Schwarz, J. S., & Heussen, K. (2022). Qualification of Initialisation Challenges in Co-Simulation setups for Integrated Energy Systems. In *10th workshop on modelling and simulation of cyber-physical energy systems (mcpes)* (pp. 1–6). doi:[10.1109/MSCPES55116.2022.9770106](https://doi.org/10.1109/MSCPES55116.2022.9770106)

Walpole, R. E., Myers, R. H., Myers, S. L., & Ye, K. (2012). The analysis of variances method. In *Probability & statistics for engineers & scientists* (9th ed., pp. 414–416). Pearson Education.

Widl, E., Engelmann, A., Fehrenbach, D., Ghazouani, S., Jensen, T. V., Leitner, B., ... Wu, Z. (2019). *An overview of the PreCISE approach used for the definition of simulation and optimization workflows* (Tech. Rep.). Austrian Institute for Technology. Retrieved from <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/206569/factsheet/en>

Widl, E., Wild, C., Heussen, K., Rikos, E., & Hoang, T.-T. (2022). Comparison of two approaches for modeling the thermal domain of multi-energy networks. In *2022 open source modelling and simulation of energy systems (osmses)* (pp. 1–6). doi:[10.1109/OSMSES54027.2022.9769129](https://doi.org/10.1109/OSMSES54027.2022.9769129)

Zadeh, L. (1965). Fuzzy sets. *Information and Control*, 8(3), 338–353. doi:[10.1016/S0019-9958\(65\)90241-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0019-9958(65)90241-X)

Zadeh, L. A. (1996). A simple view of the Dempster-Shafer theory of evidence and its implication for the rule of combination. In *Fuzzy sets, fuzzy logic, and fuzzy systems: Selected papers by Lotfi A. Zadeh* (pp. 674–679). USA: World Scientific Publishing Co., Inc.

Zhang, J., Yin, J., & Wang, R. (2020). Basic framework and main methods of uncertainty quantification. *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, 2020. doi:[10.1155/2020/6068203](https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/6068203)

Consortium

Disclaimer

All information provided reflects the status of the ERIGrid 2.0 project at the time of writing and may be subject to change.

Neither the ERIGrid 2.0 Consortium as a whole, nor any single party within the ERIGrid 2.0 Consortium warrant that the information contained in this document is capable of use, nor that the use of such information is free from risk. Neither the ERIGrid 2.0 Consortium as a whole, nor any single party within the ERIGrid 2.0 Consortium accepts any liability for loss or damage suffered by any person using the information.

This document does not represent the opinion of the European Community, and the European Community is not responsible for any use that might be made of its content.

Copyright Notice

© 2023 by the authors, the ERIGrid 2.0 consortium. This work is licensed under a "CC BY 4.0" license.

